

Open Education European Alliance Final Report: Feasibility

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1. Introduction

European countries are increasingly reviewing the role of the university, and its relationship to industry and society and are collaborating more than ever before. Digital transformation in research and education has brought about unprecedented change over the years, including an increasing open agenda that includes open education, being adopted by universities across Europe.

In the summer of 2025, SPARC Europe began some foundational work on the need for and interest in establishing a European alliance on Open Education before developing a multi-annual agenda to serve this ambition. *The Feasibility Plan for a European Alliance for Open Education (FEUR-OE) Project* sought to increase open education amongst higher education institutions to transform FAIR education and bring about longer-term system change. It had three objectives: 1) To analyse the feasibility of developing a European alliance of key stakeholders to enable a system change in the mid to long-term through collective action. 2) To define the vision, mission, value, and remit of an Open Education alliance for a wide range of stakeholders in Europe. And 3) to develop a high-level action plan to create and implement a European alliance that supports and complements local and national initiatives where feasible.

The definition of Open Education

As outlined in the [OpenEdu Framework](#),

“Open education is a way of carrying out education, often using digital technologies. Its aim is to widen access and participation to everyone by removing barriers and making learning accessible, abundant, and customisable for all. It offers multiple ways of teaching and learning, building and sharing knowledge. It also provides a variety of access routes to formal and non-formal education, and connects the two.”

As part of Open Education, the UNESCO Recommendation on OER defines OER as:

“Open Educational Resources (OER) are learning, teaching and research materials in any format and medium that reside in the public domain or are under copyright that have been released under an open license, that permit no-cost access, re-use, re-purpose, adaptation and redistribution by others.”

Both of these definitions create parts of a picture of a complex area, see also section 3.

FAIR and Open

The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles better ensures data can be found by both humans and machines, is available to others through defined conditions, can be exchanged between different systems, and can be reused. These fit well with the goals of Open Educational Resources (OER), which are similar to David Wiley's 5 R's but not the same. There is broad consensus in the Open Education community on following the 5Rs: "5Rs; 1. Retain - make, own, and control a copy of the resource (e.g., download your own copy), 2. Revise - edit, adapt, and modify your copy of the resource (e.g., translate into another language), Remix - combine your original or revised copy of the resource with other existing material(s) to create something new (e.g., make a mashup), Reuse - use your original, revised, or remixed copy of the resource publicly (e.g., in a class), Redistribute - share copies of your original, revised, or remixed copy of the resource with others (e.g., post a copy online to share with class). Some interviewees suggested applying FAIR to open education but there was no consensus on this.

This report recommends whether the open education community should move forward with the concept of developing a European Alliance for Open Education based on an evidence base. The FEUR-OE Project explores the perceptions of over 25 experts on whether there is an appetite for an alliance, identifying the needs and motivations for doing so, who and what it should focus on, what collective action challenges and opportunities might look like, and which organisations in the field this relates to. The report primarily reflects what researchers have heard from the community of this project, resulting in areas of both convergence and divergence. Key decisions will therefore need to be made on the focus of the possible alliance by its initiators and members. The priorities of numerous national and international experts have been considered: Speaking to key Dutch, Finnish, German and UK experts, as well as international Higher Education and Open Education leads from seven influential organisations with open education as one of their priorities. FEUR-OE also draws on lessons learnt from international communities of practice (COPs) worldwide as input for how and how not to develop an Alliance COP or COPs in the future, input for the later strategic part of the project.

This report concludes with recommendations making a clear case for establishing a European Alliance for Open Education. It summarises the research conducted, the process of which is described in section 2, the Methodology, including the description of the data collected to inform this report. Sections 3-7 provide a summary of the findings and recommendations based on the analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data.

Section 3 describes the remit of the alliance, outlining the mandate and goals, scope, areas to avoid, and some principles on how to run the alliance as experts see it. An adaptation of a SWOT analysis is delineated in section 4 which summarizes the strengths and opportunities of an alliance in somewhat detail and section 5 outlines the challenges and risks of an alliance. Section 6 describes a range of key stakeholders to be considered for the alliance as primarily mentioned by interviewees. Section 7 addresses some of the key learnings from an analysis of a small selection of existing communities of practice. The final part, section 8, provides a summarised list of recommendations above all drawing on sections 3-5.

An Annexe at the end of the document contains summaries and an analysis of the data collected through each step of our Methodology. Each of the sections include links to relevant parts of the Annexe where more detail can be found except for the summarised Recommendations. The Annexe itself is recommended reading to get the full scope of feedback and data received.

To start with, the next section describes the methodology used and the data collected to inform this report.

2. Methodology

The project had three phases: Phase One gathered data to test the feasibility of the Alliance concept. Phase Two delivered a report that synthesises strengths, opportunities, and challenges and risks of such an alliance, stating the feasibility of its development. Phase Three set out a high-level plan. This report is the culmination of the work executed for both Phase 1 and part of Phase 2.

Qualitative research saw SPARC Europe conduct 45-60 minute interviews with thirteen Dutch education experts and 16 international open education experts, e.g. speaking at a meeting of the Network of Open Orgs ([NOO](#)), which brings many leading international organisations in open education together on a monthly basis. As a result, we received feedback from the Community College Consortium for Open Educational Resources ([CCCOER](#)), the International Council for Open and Distance Education ([ICDE](#)), the Institute for the Study of Knowledge Management in Education ([ISKME](#)), The Knowledge Equity Network ([KEN](#)), [Open Education Global](#), and [SPARC US](#). NOO members had two more weeks to complete the online questionnaire to give everyone more time to respond. We ended the qualitative analysis by speaking to [ECIU](#) and [FOR-EU4All](#) as the European alliance of all university alliances.

SPARC Europe posed eight questions to gain an understanding of the need for an alliance, who and what it should focus on, what risks and opportunities collective action could entail, and which organisations could impact this.

All qualitative interview responses were then aggregated and anonymised. Data summaries were created for each question using a paid version of Google Gemini AI. Care was taken to ensure the underlying data, prompts, and generated content was not shared and used for model training. Summaries were then proofread and cross-referenced with the source data. Extensive edits and additions were made to ensure summaries were comprehensive, accurate, and represented the views expressed in interviews.

SPARC Europe also circulated a [short questionnaire](#) (four key questions) for some quantitative data to gauge to what extent Dutch experts considered international collaboration important for the programme to address common challenges and to what extent that might be the basis for an alliance. Answers were analysed and aggregated, and the names of efforts and organisations mentioned were also fed into the stakeholder analysis (Section 6). We received twelve responses from fourteen interviewees.

In addition, SPARC Europe analysed a range of international communities of practice in the Open Higher Education space in Europe, and globally, to inform the understanding of what it takes to run a strong alliance or community of practice. We selected a range of CoPs and organisations that address different stakeholders and approach knowledge management in the Open space in differing ways. The team looked at the Council of National Open Science Coordination ([CONOSC](#)), the Community College Consortium for Open Educational Resources ([CCCOER](#)), the European Network of Open Education Librarians ([ENOEL](#)), the Open Education Network ([OEN](#)), the [UNESCO OER Dynamic Coalition](#), and the Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#)). We analysed their strategies/visions/missions, how they are organised and operate, financing, and activity offering. We finally conducted a SWOT analysis to understand their merits and limitations bringing learnings together in a summarised table highlighting strong strategies, operational choices, key activities and approaches to sustainability.

SPARC Europe then synthesised the quantitative and qualitative research and mapped the above data to a framework similar to SWOT before writing the report. It looked at the strengths, opportunities, challenges before bringing this together in a Recommendations section remaining faithful to what the community shared at interview.

The project also conducted a stakeholder analysis for the Alliance, using its work with Connecting the Opens and data from the FEUR-OE Project. These include names of alliances,

associations/federations/networks, infrastructures/service providers, intergovernmental organisations, NGOs/NFPs, NRENs, RPOs, and others. Based on the questionnaire, interview feedback, and team knowledge, the project will use these names to select the organisations invited to the Alliance. We may expand on this list once the mandate has been agreed upon.

The Annexe provides the rich research analysis, and a list of those we interviewed.

Having provided an introduction to this feasibility report and an overview of the methodology used, the next sections provide the research results. What is the remit of a European alliance for open education?

3. The remits of an alliance

While this report primarily addresses the first objective of this feasibility plan, i.e. to analyse the feasibility of developing a European alliance of key stakeholders (EUR-OE) to enable a system change in the mid to long-term through collective action, it also starts to address the second objective: to define the vision, mission, value and remit of an Open Education alliance for a wide range of stakeholders in Europe. Based on our research findings, we summarise the perceptions of a range of stakeholders on what the remit of an alliance could be here. Additional details on all these aspects of an alliance can be found in the Annexe where we provide detailed summaries of what stakeholders said in answer to the question: “What should the remit (mandate and goals) of an international open education alliance be?”

What is meant by open education?

Data from interviews reveals that stakeholders have a very broad view of what open education entails. This is in keeping with the way open education has evolved over the years. As revealed in the report, open education encompasses Open Educational Resources, MOOCs, open pedagogies, open practices, open policies, and open licenses. The report also highlights the way that contemporary open education practices are largely done digitally so in that context open education also typically involves technologies which leads to calls for open infrastructure (hardware and software that constitute learning systems) along with associated needs for open standards and interoperability to ensure ease of sharing and reuse. The report also reveals an awareness that in the digital context practices of open education invariably involve data including meta data about resources and student data about learning. The scope of open education is broad and cross cutting.

It is generally agreed that an international open education alliance should have a comprehensive mandate focused on accelerating digital transformation in education through collective action, shared standards, and a unified vision, transcending national boundaries. We have garnered many ideas for the mandate and scope of such an alliance, and some conflict with one another, e.g. focus on policy change vs seek to implement technology solutions. The following sub-sections collate them without prioritising one point over another. Ideally, members of the first Alliance collaboratively agree on a mission, vision, and mandate and then sign up to a memorandum of understanding.

3.1 Mandate and goals

The possible mandate and goals for a European Alliance for Open Education are wide-ranging, including:

- Unifying and harmonising policies
- Shaping a European shared understanding and approach to open education
- Standardisation and interoperability
- Quality
- Connecting digital infrastructure
- Knowledge and expertise exchange
- Creating a movement and culture shift to openness and collaboration
- Stimulating innovation

The majority see knowledge exchange and collective learning—sharing successes and failures in policy and practice—as a key function for addressing common challenges and accelerating the digital transition. Other frequently raised topics are developing a shared understanding and definition of Open Education and the value of OER, and establishing a common agenda or vision and process. And how does OE shape the future of teaching?

The alliance could be seen as a way of creating an open education movement where all stakeholders act together, reframing the conversation around open education from being a niche topic to one central to the future of teaching and the fundamental purpose of education itself. We need to advocate for open education being at the forefront of educational innovation, and connecting it to digital transformation and AI. On AI: Interviewees reveal an awareness of the impact of AI on education in general, and open education in particular. Its impact on OE is at a very early stage and evolving. The report highlights ways in which incorporating AI into the efforts of the Alliance could strengthen the work of the alliance.

The ultimate goal should be to create a vibrant, connected community empowered to shape the future of open education. A community rooted in shared values, not just a collection of projects. Rather than duplicating the work of existing organisations, its primary mission should be to connect, strengthen, and amplify them, also providing a clearer entry point into a country's open education landscape. A new collaboration through an alliance between various stakeholders, bridging islands, can make a stronger, integrated collective with shared goals, potentially acting as an influential collective voice. A future alliance can thereby potentially increase the visibility of open education amongst key decision-makers and policymakers and take action in a new integrated way.

An international open education alliance—especially with a European focus—should influence open education policy at the European level. It can have a unique role as a central policy advocate lobbying governments/ministries to align their policies with the values of open education and knowledge as a public good. It could also connect to broader significant European and global priorities, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the European Council Recommendation on micro-credentialing and lifelong learning. This would give the alliance a powerful narrative for collaboration and shows how open education contributes to a more sustainable and equitable world, not just in formal academic communities, but for everyone.

The new alliance could also provide a knowledge hub, one that also facilitates peer learning and knowledge exchange, supporting the practical implementation of open education and problem-solving. Addressing quality, creating unified international standards, e.g. for OER usage, identification, improving OER discoverability, interoperability challenges, and infrastructure collectively would also be important topics to address. The alliance could provide a more practical and inclusive narrative beyond open content, including open practices and pedagogy. Raising awareness of the challenges and solutions in OE and training educators and decision makers to advocate for change was regularly mentioned. This includes tackling ownership issues, a common language, the integration of OER into curriculum design, and the equitable distribution of knowledge in the age of AI. This can form the basis of joint projects and funding efforts for European solutions to bigger problems. The alliance could also serve as a key education innovation hub for experimentation and incubation with new forms of open materials, tools, technologies and new curriculum models and strategies, particularly around open teaching. Not only that, the alliance could host safe spaces where candid discussions can take place on tough topics like the balance between being open and commercial exploitation.

The alliance's role should be primarily facilitative: stimulating, guiding, enabling, and advocating, rather than directly implementing solutions for individual institutions or countries. It should add to, rather than duplicate, national initiatives.

For additional details, see the Dutch Expert Interview Summary [Annexe B](#) (especially the answer to question 4) and International Stakeholders Interview Summary [Annexe C](#) (especially the answer to question 3).

3.2 Scope

Alliance activities could address a wide range of stakeholders for systemic change: from students and teachers to senior higher education leadership to national and international change agents, policymakers and funders. Who it serves depends on the alliance's mandate and scope.

While initial efforts should focus on universities of applied science and research universities, the mandate could extend to addressing the unique needs of vocational and further education (mentioned by few in our interviews), which have largely been overlooked in the open education movement. Furthermore, lifelong learning could also be part of the mandate, providing flexible learning pathways and credentials, and efforts should ultimately benefit the labour market by ensuring that learners acquire in-demand skills. One respondent suggested that primary and secondary education might also be included for a more holistic, transformative impact.

A common view was that public values should be central to the effort and championed. While the goal of "open" was not questioned for the majority, in some instances, it was pointed out that one should explore pragmatic pathways to openness, especially when engaging with commercial entities or in contexts where full openness is challenging or in conflict with certain priorities. The alliance could perhaps build its own ecosystem to counter publishers and big tech's growing capture of education services, data, and content.

More broadly, the alliance could address institutional legal, teaching, and technology issues, especially those around which there is a collective will for change.

While a European focus makes sense due to existing initiatives and shared values, a global approach could provide even greater value by including diverse perspectives and addressing common challenges.

3.3 Areas to avoid

The alliance must not replicate what other European organisations or networks are already doing, nor act as a vendor. Instead, it should act as an enabler, international convenor and influencer. Its mandate should be clearly defined to fill a unique niche and add value by bringing existing groups together. An international pen education alliance must respect institutional identity and autonomy, ensuring institutional sovereignty is not compromised. An alliance should therefore refrain from direct involvement in core activities that are primarily the domain of individual institutions, such as teaching and valorisation and liaising directly with teaching staff. Instead, it should provide support through national and institutional structures to support transformative change.

The alliance should not focus on short-term learning goals but on larger, overarching ones aligned with European values that promote long-term, systemic transformation. However, goals should neither be too high-level nor too vague. The alliance should conduct practical, actionable activities that address the needs of practitioners. It should empower practitioners by equipping them with resources, fostering networks, and cultivating a shared sense of purpose. The alliance should avoid developing a single product or open education solution and instead concentrate on fostering relationships and partnerships. A focus could be on interoperability and connecting existing resources. Priority here should be given to flexible, “just enough, just in time” technologies rather than becoming entangled in large, unwieldy systems.

Finally, the alliance should have a clear strategy before intensively engaging with its stakeholders. It should not include organisations that use open education as a way to attract users only to introduce fees later or seek lock-in to their platform or service.

3.4 Running the alliance

A stable, dedicated funding stream that supports an office and staff is vital for the alliance to make the intended progress. Dedicated staff is crucial for maintaining momentum as progress will be slow without it. A hybrid model could also work well: a central team funded by a stable source, supplemented by shared staff resources from member organisations. This model ensures core work gets done while leveraging the expertise of the wider network. Given the demands on time, the alliance should make it easy for people to get involved and disengage as needed. A flexible model would encourage participation without overwhelming individuals.

Keeping the alliance's operational model simple and efficient is important. A complex governance or funding structure could become a barrier to progress.

3.5 The audience

3.5.1 Who the alliance should serve

Although who the alliance serves will ultimately depend on its mandate, an international open education alliance should serve a broad range of stakeholders, clearly focusing on the learner as the ultimate beneficiary. The alliance should bring idealists and pragmatists together. It should build strategic partnerships with those who have policy and funding influence on the one hand, and those with a wider community that provides ground-level expertise on the other.

The primary audience for the alliance should be decision-makers at the highest levels, i.e. policymakers and funders at institutional, regional, national, and European levels who drive and implement systemic change by influencing legislation, funding, and broader educational agendas. On an institutional level, senior higher education leaders such as rectors or vice-rectors/chancellors and internationalisation policy advisors have important roles, as do the national rectors' conferences.

System change agents such as SURF, JISC, Kennisnet, and NRENs are crucial stakeholders because they have a system-wide mandate to support digital transformation. This makes them essential partners for infrastructure and service development. They can also serve as national nodes for the alliance for broader European collaboration. Technology professionals are critical for building and maintaining the necessary digital infrastructure, managing data, such as analytics or ownership, and addressing technical and legal issues related to sharing and interoperability.

Having ministries, system change agents and educational leadership at the table is not enough; the alliance must also engage those directly involved in the practical realities of education. Both a top-down and bottom-up approach is needed to scale open education and make policymaking achievable, informed by realities on the ground. It is essential to talk *with* educators, i.e. teachers, instructional designers, librarians, and pedagogy experts, rather than merely *about* education. As the implementers of open education practices, they are a critical beneficiary, needing support, resources, and recognition for their efforts in bringing about change in open education.

The alliance should also serve a wider ecosystem of stakeholders, including developers and learning designers who are essential for building and maintaining collaborative digital ecosystems and agreeing on licensing models. Legal experts can help develop standards and resolve complex licensing and intellectual property issues. Intermediary or umbrella organisations that work on the ground and face similar challenges can provide a way to scale up local successes, and this can include libraries.

Commercial service providers could also participate under certain conditions, with certain safeguards in place (still to be determined), but not as full voting members due to their inherent profit-driven models, which can conflict with the public values of open education. They would be essential for strategic discussions.

The alliance's success will depend on its ability to forge a powerful, unified collective that prioritises public values and learner well-being, while strategically engaging all necessary parties to achieve its transformative goals.

Finally, to achieve its transformative aims, the alliance must deliver tangible benefits to its members—particularly practitioners. With job cuts and diminishing funding in Higher Education, participants need assurance that their engagement is worthwhile.

3.5.2 Membership

The alliance should be strategic about who is "at the table." A good governance structure is vital. Limits to participation need to be defined. Upholding and advancing public values could be seen as fundamental principles of membership. The alliance should differentiate members with voting rights from observers, partners, and beneficiaries.

Members could include senior leadership from educational Institutions and other policymakers, system change agents, national education/digitisation bodies, including NRENs, international umbrella organisations, such as UNESCO, RDA, EUA, LERU, OAPEN, European federations of

employers and teachers, national rectors conferences, societal actors such as NGOs, some service providers and activists championing public values.

Experts will be needed to progress certain themes forwarded through expert groups or as topic chairs. They should not have to be members. These could include government advisors, project or change managers, HR, libraries, information managers, and researchers. Initiatives or “squads” could engage countries not yet involved in open education.

3.5.3 Who is potentially interested in participating in the alliance

International stakeholder interviewees unanimously expressed interest in being part of an alliance though with a variety of caveats and conditions including wanting the alliance to aim high and create a movement. Those who expressed interest include:

[ECIU](#) University: RPO alliance

European University Alliances ([FOREU4All](#)): RPO alliance

The International Council for Open and Distance Education ([ICDE](#)): NGO/NFP

[JISC](#), UK: NREN

[Knowledge Equity Network](#), UK: Initiative

[Open Education Global](#): NGO/NFP

[ORCA.nrw](#), Stifterverband, Germany: NGO/NFP

[Stifterverband](#), Germany: NGO/NFP

Having described the potential remit of an international alliance on open education, Section 4 looks at a range of strengths and opportunities associated with establishing an alliance.

4. The strengths and opportunities of an alliance

4.1 Strengths

4.1.1 Making the strong, stronger

Some countries, like the Netherlands, are taking a holistic and strategic approach to digital transformation in education encompassing technology, pedagogy, and policy on a large scale. However, for transformative educational change to occur, a nation can only realise higher ambitions collectively on an international stage to develop shared infrastructure, standards, and make necessary cultural shifts in areas such as:

- Dealing with big tech and edtech - digital sovereignty. Acting together in conversations with suppliers.
- Setting standards for sharing open teaching materials.
- Ensuring collaborative agreements place public values above the interests of commercial parties.
- Agreeing on what constitutes a common, basic, knowledge-sharing infrastructure.
- Developing supportive legislation and regulation.
- Enhancing the quality of education by learning and innovating together, including removing barriers to enable more flexible use of educational offerings.
- Working together to formulate new forms and agreements to provide ICT systems and digital education resources.
- Enabling transformation by creating new governance, management, organisation, and financing forms.

For more details, see [Question 1 of the Dutch Expert Questionnaire Summary](#) in [Annexe A](#).

4.1.2 Strength in numbers: European partners

Countries and organisations across Europe and beyond are engaged in transformative change in education and their existence suggests a growing impetus for collaboration and that now is a timely opportunity for creating an alliance. The project identified over 50 organisations innovating in education and open education. This large number of organisations could be the starting point for building a strong alliance with strength in numbers and complementary strengths that can be leveraged for mutual benefit. For a list of these organisations, see Section 6.

Creating an alliance requires a backbone organisation with the standing and reputation to initiate and lead the effort. One or more organisations will act as founders, providing the backbone and leadership required.

4.1.3 Strength in shared interests and goals

A strong alliance is built on a foundation of common objectives. Dutch experts identified the following ambitions that can only or better be realised by working with others internationally:

1. Addressing big tech and edtech market power
2. Facilitating the sharing and reuse of learning materials
3. Fostering a culture of Openness and collaboration
4. Building and connecting digital infrastructure
5. Agreeing on standards and interoperability
6. Influencing international policy and legislation
7. Promoting recognition and reward for open practices
8. Strategic resource allocation and sustainability

Of the areas, “Fostering a Culture of Openness and Collaboration”, “Building and Connecting Digital Infrastructure” and “Agreeing on Standards and Interoperability” were most prevalent although interviewees were not asked to rank importance. Agreeing on, and prioritising, the preferred direction and focus will necessitate collaboration. Were an alliance to be established, a structured process would need to define these and agree on common objectives.

1. *Fostering a culture of openness and collaboration:* A significant transformation and cultural shift is necessary. Infrastructure and materials are important, but the culture shift entails a reframing of learning and a broader education concept. This change process requires the creation of a shared mindset based on a different way of looking at education. Openness, sharing, collaboration, and connecting are integral to this new mindset. Making this culture shift requires addressing fear of sharing, a shift to finding, reusing and maintaining quality resources, learning new pedagogical practices, and changing systems of reward and recognition. The culture shift entails working as a network of institutions and envisioning what a field or discipline as a whole looks like, but can only be achieved by collective work as a network. An international alliance brings together collective efforts toward this culture shift, providing a powerful platform for "learning together," exchanging good practices, and gaining a broader perspective on successes and challenges. The combined efforts of international

initiatives can generate the “why” of this new way of learning, along with associated stories and motivations that create a shared mindset among educators, directors, and policymakers, moving from individual efforts to a unified movement.

2. Building and connecting digital infrastructure: While many countries have the capacity to develop national infrastructure, collaborating internationally would create a stronger, more interconnected system. A shared European-wide technical vision, a set of frameworks for connecting what we do with what they do, and an ecosystem process for sharing and linking infrastructure would help enable flexible learning and student mobility across countries. Interoperable infrastructures are needed for working with and sharing learning materials, credentials, student IDs, digital wallets, personalised learning pathways, and community learning. Institutional digital infrastructures and those used directly by educators must be included. Sharing existing infrastructure, learning from the successes and pitfalls of others, and actively linking various national infrastructures benefit all. An international alliance platform for exchanging knowledge is needed to enable this process.

3. Agreeing on standards and interoperability: Achieving seamless learning without borders fundamentally relies on international standardisation. This includes agreeing on standards for data exchange, digital wallets, student IDs, credentials, skills and learning outcomes, and personalised learning pathways. Standardisation includes agreeing collectively on what open means, encompassing concepts like the commons, technical standards (e.g. FAIR), and machine readability. Standards and systems for sharing knowledge need to be agreed on. While national standards are a starting point, validating and adapting them to international needs and cultures is vital. Collectively building an open education European interoperability framework provides the opportunity to move beyond national "our standards" to a shared, internationally recognised approach. An international alliance provides the means for creating and implementing shared European standards.

4. Addressing big tech and edtech market power: To effectively counter the market dominance of large technology and education technology companies, we need to collaborate on a European or even global scale. National initiatives alone are insufficient to influence these influential international players. An international alliance provides a way of building market power on the demand side. A unified international alliance provides a strong foundation for negotiating terms and conditions on the use of learning materials and ensuring that public

values are upheld in digital learning environments and agreements. An international alliance mitigates significant tech challenges to digital sovereignty by establishing alternative ways of sourcing infrastructure and services.

5. Facilitating the sharing and reuse of learning materials: Although there's a recognised need for infrastructure to share learning materials, the "why" and motivation for sharing aren't always clear to individual educators, directors, policymakers and national leaders. International collaboration can bolster the case for sharing. International materials for subjects like health care, nursing, IT, engineering, and agriculture, and others that transcend national borders, make flexible cross-border learning possible. Student mobility necessitates internationally available and reusable materials. Overcoming the inherent difficulty of sharing materials (even within an institution) becomes more feasible with international impetus and proven models of quality content that can be reused. An international alliance can build a common curriculum and share it. Ultimately, an international alliance can enhance how learning materials are developed, adopted, reused, and maintained.

6. Influencing international policy and legislation: For higher education, impacting policies and legislation at the European level necessitates an international alliance. A strong, collective agenda from multiple countries is needed to effectively influence these broader discussions and ensure that the culture shift associated with this new vision of education is supported by policy and legislation, including those that foster learning without barriers, student and labour mobility, international standards, and ensure the long-term sustainability of open practices. An international alliance provides a means for sharing and learning from existing policy and collectively drafting new policy. Existing successful research and open science policies from across the alliance can provide a useful model to learn from. An international alliance could be a very effective way of influencing AI and education legislation and policy at the European level.

7. Promoting recognition and reward for open practices: A significant barrier to wider adoption of open practices is the lack of formal recognition and reward for teaching staff and faculty who engage in open work, collaboration, and sharing. An international ambition or mechanism for recognising open contributions, such as open textbooks, would be a significant step forward. Academic career development within and across institutions must include recognition of open work, highlighting the benefits of reuse, and wider impact. An international alliance could establish precedents for appointing full professors based on their impact in open

scholarship, fostering a system-wide change that values contributions beyond traditional research outputs.

8. Strategic resource allocation and sustainability: While national funding is essential, international alliances can provide access to broader funding landscapes and support the longevity of open infrastructure initiatives that often struggle with project-based financing. In some countries, ministerial interest in open education has waned.

An international alliance can reignite ministerial interest. By working together, countries can ensure a more efficient and impactful use of public money, creating a sustainable ecosystem for open education and open science.

International stakeholder interviewees expressed interest in an alliance especially for addressing systemic challenges in a unified manner. Areas of interest for an alliance include:

- Policy and influence
- Collaboration and knowledge exchange
- Standardisation and technical interoperability
- Global and cultural relevance

For more details on all of these see [Annexe C](#) Question [1](#).

In addition, international stakeholders believe an alliance can help them directly accomplish their own mission and goals particularly around:

- Policy and advocacy
- Unify a European approach to open education
- Collaboration and community building
- Create a shared digital infrastructure
- Facilitate peer learning and knowledge exchange
- Provide safe spaces
- Quality and Innovation
- Driving innovation

For more details on all of these see Questions [3](#) and [4](#) in [Annexe C](#).

On a practical level, many international stakeholders share similar goals and perceive an alliance as a means of helping them accomplish them.

4.2 Opportunities

4.2.1 Accomplish more together than apart

Dutch stakeholders identified the following challenges and opportunities that can only or better be realised through collective international action:

1. Overcoming national silos and fostering collective thinking
2. Influencing publishers and big tech
3. Establishing and adopting international standards
4. Shifting teaching culture and adapting to rapid change
5. Securing funding and sustainable infrastructure
6. Harmonising policies and practices

International stakeholders see the advantages and goals of an international alliance as enabling:

- Policy advocacy
- Shaping a European approach to open education
- Collaboration, community building and knowledge exchange
- Connection to broader initiatives
- Standardisation and technical interoperability
- Quality and Innovation

For more details, see questions [1](#), [3](#) and [4](#) of the [International Stakeholders Interviews Summary](#) in [Annexe C](#).

To identify more clearly common ground for an alliance, we found areas of opportunity that emerged through our different research methodologies as follows:

POLICY

- Harmonising policies and practices
- Policy advocacy
- Influencing international policy and legislation

STANDARDS & INTEROPERABILITY

- Establishing and adopting international standards
- Standardisation and technical interoperability
- Agreeing on standards and interoperability

CULTURE CHANGE

- Shifting teaching culture and adapting to rapid change
- Fostering a culture of Openness and collaboration
- Facilitating the sharing and reuse of learning materials
- Promoting recognition and reward for open practices

A EUROPEAN APPROACH TO OPEN EDUCATION

- Overcoming national silos and fostering collective thinking
- Collaboration, community building and knowledge exchange
- Shaping a European approach to open education
- Connection to broader initiatives

DEALING WITH BIG TECH & EDTECH

- Influencing publishers and big tech
- Addressing big tech and edtech market power

DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND SUSTAINABILITY

- Building and connecting digital infrastructure
- Securing funding and sustainable infrastructure
- Strategic resource allocation and sustainability

QUALITY & INNOVATION

- Quality and Innovation

These common interests create a potential set of shared strategic goals that can give the alliance cohesion and focus. An alliance can establish a common agenda with shared priorities to foster collaborative efforts rather than redundant individual initiatives. It can also ensure that a common agenda has unique selling points so as not to duplicate efforts.

A key opportunity is to transition the current patchwork of fragmented open education initiatives and organisations into a cohesive, coordinated whole. It would be invaluable to join forces and work together toward an interoperable European approach to open education, including a common definition and common implementation process.

An alliance could serve as an innovation hub for experimentation and incubation, exploring new forms of open materials (e.g. modular, easily modifiable content), infrastructure, rewards and recognition. Curriculum development models and strategies could be examined not just the resource. An alliance could co-create and share a curriculum and pioneer new approaches to teaching and learning.

An alliance has the opportunity to create a shared common voice for advocacy and for policy. This collective voice can influence governments, policymakers, and powerful international publishers and tech providers. A collective stance is crucial for negotiating favourable agreements on terms and conditions for learning materials and infrastructures. It is also key for advocating for changes in national and European funding structures, rules, and regulations that are in the way of openness.

An alliance can collectively coordinate, enlarge, and sustain open content, collections, and credentials based on openness. This has the potential to enable flexible cross-border learning opportunities and higher-quality materials and teaching practices.

A European collective effort could pool and target funding to address common needs, amplifying benefits and impact across countries.

4.2.2 Build bridges and connections

An alliance is seen as a means of connecting ministries, policymakers, and system change agents across countries.

In addition, it can serve as a bridge between practitioners and those with decision-making authority, creating crucial connecting tissue within and between national open education initiatives.

It can bring together diverse stakeholders – teachers, support staff, management, librarians, NRENs, national policy bodies, and institutions – who currently operate in silos but face similar challenges and share common questions.

Collaborating internationally to build and connect digital Infrastructure creates a stronger, more interconnected system. As part of this infrastructure an alliance can establish a shared European wide technical vision and promote international interoperable standards helping accelerate an interconnected digital transition across Europe.

A connected alliance can unify a European approach to open education and build a broad European movement that is uniquely open with a common direction.

For more details, see answers in [Dutch Expert Interview Summary Annexe B](#) and [International Stakeholders Interview Summary Annexe C](#).

4.2.3 Sharing of knowledge and expertise

An alliance can facilitate peer learning and knowledge exchange. Connecting experts from different countries helps them learn from each other's successful practices. Sharing best practices helps identify emerging trends and accelerate the digital transition across Europe and beyond. An alliance can help institutional leaders think about the sector as a whole, not just their institution. It can promote a learning together ethos, fostering social change and a shared open mindset across institutions and countries.

A community of practice is one key way an alliance can enable knowledge exchange. The Learning from Communities of Practice section of this report (Section 7) provides opportunities associated with a community of practice and guidance related to strategy, operations, activities, and sustainability of COPs.

An alliance can serve as a vital network for information and knowledge exchange of digital strategies and policy approaches, allowing different countries and institutions to learn from each other.

Alliance knowledge exchange should focus not just on strategy and policy but on the how-to of open education — providing guidance, methodologies, and blueprints for implementing open education, including effectively using digital tools and infrastructure. This includes sharing lifecycle management models for Open Educational Resources (OER) and strategies for integrating OER into course design. An alliance focused on the practical application of open education can overcome barriers and show tangible benefits, moving beyond simple advocacy.

An international learning community approach provides support, shared stories, and validation for institutions and individuals striving to change deeply ingrained practices and ensure recognition and reward for open work.

An alliance can create safe, open, and transparent forums for candid discussions about difficult topics like the balance between being open and the fear of commercial exploitation of one's work. These safe spaces, built on trust and a shared mission, would provide the confidence needed for individuals and institutions to fully embrace open practices.

An alliance can establish international expert working groups to collaborate on topics and activities of shared interest.

Being open is not just a technological concept but a cultural shift and way of thinking. Collective knowledge exchange and expertise could build a movement forward with this cultural shift and transformation of education.

For more details, see answers [Dutch Expert Interview Summary Annexe B](#) and [International Stakeholders Interview Summary Annexe C](#).

While there are considerable strengths and opportunities associated with an alliance there are also a number of risks and challenges.

5. Challenges and risks for an open education alliance

These 22 challenges and risks have been drawn from all interviews conducted. They have been organised into eight categories: from those related to the ambition or scope, to issues of collaboration vs sovereignty, or how organisation and action can cause challenges to the importance of monitoring and the alliance's sustainability.

Note: A risk register that describes the probability and mitigation of some of these risks should be developed together with the first members of the alliance since collective knowledge on how to address them as a joint responsibility is key. This will serve as a sound basis for building a strong alliance through collective international solutions.

AMBITION

- I. Transformation in education is limited in scope to open education.
- II. The alliance is project-based rather than a transformational change organisation or initiative focusing on mid to longer-term systemic change.
- III. Working collaboratively may require concessions and could delay local progress.

SCOPE

- IV. Not having a clearly defined mandate and scope of activities, and trying to do too much "everything for everyone".
- V. There is no collective agreement on the fundamentals behind the alliance's scope, e.g. higher education vs. vocational education, open vs. FAIR, policy vs. practice, resources vs. process, non-commercial vs. commercial.
- VI. Finding common ground on focus areas broad enough to engage the majority is unattainable.
- VII. Local challenges are not easily addressed internationally, e.g. differences in legal contexts.

COLLABORATION

- VIII. Too little focus is placed on understanding the diverse needs of key stakeholders/change enablers to impact progress in open education.
- IX. Not sufficiently investing in relationships and collaboration, such as practitioners bringing in the community perspective, impedes change in open education.
- X. Not including those involved in the change process early on may result in more resistance and slower change.
- XI. Too few impactful members of the alliance exist to mobilise change.

ORGANISATION

- XII. A backbone organisation with sufficient standing and reputation is not found for the alliance.

SOVEREIGNTY

- XIII. Interference in institutional sovereignty risks threatening the broad adoption of OE in HE, e.g. by making it a top-down prescriptive body, getting involved in institutional valorisation, or centralising efforts too much.

ACTION

- XIV. A lack of a strategy and concrete results does not yield the expected results.
- XV. Too much discussion: “talking shops” occur at the expense of concrete, tangible outputs contributing to OE implementation.
- XVI. Too many small projects are managed ineffectively.

MONITORING

- XVII. The alliance does not monitor, grasp and act on the impact of new technological developments on its activities.
- XVIII. Understanding change outside Europe, e.g. in the Global South, requires too many resources and hampers change in Europe.

SUSTAINABILITY

- XIX. Sustainability issues stop efforts prematurely.
- XX. Too heavy reliance on voluntary, unpaid or in-kind contributions may significantly slow efforts.
- XXI. Transformation initiatives require a long-term commitment, but many organisations rely on short-term, project-based funding.
- XXII. Financial constraints threaten to prioritise revenue-making over openness.

For more details, see answers to [Question 6](#) and [Question 8](#), and to a lesser extent [Question 3](#), in [Annexe B](#) and answers in the International Interview Summary [Annexe C](#).

Realising the identified strengths and opportunities — as well as addressing the associated risks and challenges — will require the involvement of a range of stakeholders.

6. Key stakeholders

During consultation with various stakeholders, over 50 organisations and services were identified that seek transformational change and/or leaders who could be members of the alliance. These also include some of the organisations we interviewed. They have the potential to be partners/members of the alliance. While these initiatives have similar goals, they vary in scope, focus, and levels of strategic integration. However, there are ample opportunities for collaboration around areas of common interest. Countries and institutions operate with different organisational logics, governance structures, and conceptions of roles.

Most organisations were not mentioned more than once. Hence, there seems to be a blind spot in knowing who works in the field and a lack of international collaboration.

They can be categorised into various groups: alliances, associations/federations/networks, EU organisations, infrastructures/service providers, intergovernmental organisations, NGOs/NFPs, NRENs, NRENs, intergovernmental organisations, RPOs, and others. These organisations need to be evaluated for potential inclusion in an international alliance.

1. Association of Learning Technology ([ALT](#))
2. [Aurora University Alliance](#)
3. Collaboration of European National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) ([GEANT](#))
4. [CORDA Campus](#), Belgium
5. [CSC](#) - IT Center for Science, Finland
6. [DIGIVISIO2030](#), CSC, Finland
7. [ECIU](#)
8. [EDUCAUSE](#)
9. [EOSC Association](#), Belgium
10. European University Continuing Education Network ([Eucen](#))
11. European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training ([CEDEFOP](#))
12. European Commission ([EC](#))
13. [European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan](#) (DG EAC, DG Connect)
14. European Digital Education Hub ([EDEH](#)) x2
15. European Federation of Education Employers ([EFEE](#))
16. European MOOC Consortium
17. The European Trade Union Committee for Education ([ETUCE](#))
18. European University Association ([EUA](#))

19. European University Information Systems organization ([EUNIS](#))
20. European University Institute ([EUI](#))
21. European University Alliances ([FOREU4All](#))
22. The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services ([SCOSS](#))
23. [Hochschulforum Digitalisierung](#) (HFD), Germany x 2
24. [JISC](#), UK
25. The International Council for Open and Distance Education ([ICDE](#))
26. <https://ki-campus.org/>, Germany
27. [Knowledge Equity Network](#), UK
28. [Kennisset](#), NL
29. [KLASCement](#), Belgium
30. [LaDok](#), Sweden
31. League of European Research Universities ([LERU](#))
32. Norwegian Digital Learning Arena ([NDLA](#)), Norway
33. Netherlands Initiative for Educational Research ([NRO](#)), Netherlands
34. Network of Open Orgs ([NOO](#))
35. Nordic Gateway for Research and Education ([NORDUnet](#))
36. [Npuls](#), Netherlands
37. Online Library of Open Access Books ([OAPEN](#)), Netherlands
38. [OpenAire](#), Greece
39. [Open Education Austria](#)
40. [Open Education Global](#)
41. [ORCA.nrw](#), Stifterverband, Germany
42. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development ([OECD](#))
43. [RedCLARA](#)
44. Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#))
45. [SPARC Europe](#)
46. [Stifterverband](#), Germany
47. [SURE](#), NL
48. [Technische Informationsbibliothek](#) (TIB), Germany
49. The European Association of Distance Teaching Universities ([EADTU](#))
50. United Nations for Education Science & Culture Organization ([UNESCO](#)) x 2
51. [WirLernenOnline](#), Germany
52. [XERTE](#), Aperio Foundation, US

Other organisations not mentioned could also be included in the alliance, including Association of European Research Librarians (LIBER), [Anthology](#), [Digital Public Goods](#), [D2L](#), [edX](#), the [European Commission Joint Research Centre](#), [EDEN Digital Learning Europe](#), European Digital UniverCity Alliance ([EDUC](#)), [GO-GN](#), [ILIAS](#), [LIBER](#), [Khan Academy](#), [Moodle](#), [OpenFuture](#), [Open Knowledge Foundation](#), [Science Europe](#), and [UN Global Pulse](#).

Very few organisations were mentioned as being admired for their leadership in this space. This may reflect a lack of international collaboration. Admiration was expressed for organisational leaders in this work: LERU, RDA, Opin.fi, and LaDok, who do not all significantly work in education or open education.

Existing alliances often establish a Community of Practice (CoP) as a key means of enabling collaboration and action. Given the importance of this strategic choice, an analysis of existing communities of practice was done as part of assessing the feasibility of creating a European alliance for open education. The next section describes key takeaways and learnings from that analysis.

Figure 1. Organisations seeking transformational change and/or leaders who could be members of the alliance

7. Learning from communities of practice

This section provides some insights on what it means to set up, run and sustain a Community of Practice, one form or part of the alliance.

Our analysis covers six communities of practice operating on an international scale, though not all are centred on open education. These included the Council of National Open Science Coordination ([CONOSC](#)), Community College Consortium for Open Educational Resources ([CCCOER](#)), European Network of Open Education Librarians ([ENOEL](#)), the Open Education Network ([OEN](#)), the [UNESCO OER Dynamic Coalition](#), and the Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#)).

We evaluated them on four levels: their strategic approaches, operations, activities, and how they sustained themselves. We also used the SWOT methodology to assess their general performance and then synthesised the results into the table below.

Strategy	Operations
<p><i>Purpose.</i> Establish COP purpose. Collectively as a community, generate a vision, mission and strategy/priority-setting" that includes a work plan.</p>	<p>Dedicated staff, e.g. Director, Community Manager, Director of Community Engagement, Programme Coordinator, Administrator, or others to liaise, organise, host, manage, facilitate, devise and implement a programme of events and activities.</p>
<p><i>Focus.</i> Define the geographical and organisational breadth of membership. Focus on specific education sectors. Target specific stakeholders, understanding their needs. Define organisational types eligible for membership. Identify members as multipliers in the first instance, and also large, prestigious networks. Take a staged approach to grow the network.</p>	<p>Create community governance structures, e.g. executive council, committees, and working groups, that ensure the direction and activities of the COP are guided and led by community members. And build member capacity in this area. Be agile and not too bureaucratic, so defining terms of reference is essential. <i>(Risks: members change job roles vs staff do all the work. Member prof. development and stepping into leadership roles.)</i> Consider recognition of CoP membership, e.g. badging.</p>

<p><i>Value Creation.</i></p> <p>Establish parameters for participation that ensure mutually beneficial value creation, collaborative effort and open sharing.</p> <p>Clearly define the benefits of (regularly) participating and the ways of participating.</p>	<p>Identify, install and maintain digital infrastructure for the COP.</p> <p>Focus on IT that fosters relationship-building between COP members, e.g. discussion, documentation and document sharing, virtual presentation, resource sharing, collaboration, including multilingual tools, post-and-answer questions, and shared infrastructure related to alliance collaborative projects.</p> <p>Create a website that defines the community, what takes place there and how to become a member.</p>
<p>Consider establishing some guiding principles or a code of conduct.</p>	
<p>Establish a membership acquisition plan. It depends on size and focus.</p>	
<p>Consider how to monitor and measure COP impact (tangible and intangible).</p>	
<p>Activities</p>	<p>Sustainability</p>
<p>Source activities from members and invite them to be presenters, facilitators, and knowledge-exchangers.</p> <p>Encourage activity leadership amongst members over time.</p>	<p>Explore defining business model choices, such as annual membership fees, that contribute to covering COP costs.</p> <p>Consider waiving or lowering fees in specific contextual situations.</p>
<p>Conduct workshops, webinars, and other forms of knowledge exchange. Consider developing and implementing a European OE capacity-building programme.</p>	<p>Identify and manage ways for in-kind support, where a member provides staffing, specific expertise, services, infrastructure, or other support services.</p>
<p>Establish means for members to connect, e.g. a listserv to support Q&A activity among members. This establishes relationships and allows members to learn from each other quickly.</p>	<p>Consider what is free to everyone, what is only available for members, and what has additional costs, e.g. conferences and events.</p>

Offer professional development, e.g. certificate programmes. Consider using existing open education certificate programmes available under an open licence for reuse, e.g. partnerships with existing certificate providers.	Explore partnerships with other communities for increased collaboration.
Define activities that allow for large or small commitments for a sound work balance. Enable episodic contribution and longer-term commitment by diversifying the level of engagement required.	Define an interim budget and work plan.
Host an annual event: for members/non-members.	
Consider targeting regional OE development and organising work within regions.	

Table 1. Analysis of six communities of practice as feedback for designing FEUR-OE

For more details, see [Annexe D](#).

Sections 3 through 7 have provided summaries of findings and recommendations. For a complete overview of all the findings it is recommended that you read the Annexes. The final recommendation is a synthesis of the research findings.

8. Recommendation

In short, there is unanimous agreement that enhanced international collaboration is essential for meaningful change, and there is a clearly articulated call for a broad European open education alliance from a range of professionals, experts, and organisations. Based on our research, the likelihood of an alliance forming is therefore plausible. Its feasibility depends on one or more strong backbone organisations leading the effort, supported by a mix of financial and in-kind resources. Success will require a clear mission, a strategic plan with tangible outcomes, early and meaningful engagement with key stakeholders, and sustained investment in impactful relationships throughout the process.

Transformative educational change means acting collectively on an international stage. An alliance can help build a shared and impactful community and supporting infrastructure. An alliance further enables the development of common standards and cultural shifts necessary for a truly borderless and equitable learning environment through open education.

We have brought together ideas from a diverse group of experts, and the perceived mandate, scope, and goals show a wealth of opportunities for a potential alliance. This makes the feasibility of an alliance more likely, as we identify a range of points of engagement for multiple stakeholders who can enable transformative change. Given the differences in ideas on several levels, for a successful alliance to take shape, it is important that the founding members of the alliance agree collectively on a clearly defined mission, vision, scope and mandate after discussing key principles, directions, and ambitions since being something for everyone will not achieve concrete progress.

It is essential to find common ground on areas broad enough to make transformative change in the mid to long term. Targeting common key areas such as policy, standards and interoperability, culture change, a European approach to open education, dealing with big tech and edtech, digital infrastructure and sustainability and quality and innovation will bring transformation. However, key decisions will need to be made on whether the focus of the alliance is to serve higher education and vocational education, open vs. FAIR, policy and/or practice, resources vs. process or on non-commercial and commercial.

Future directions for an alliance are grouped into four areas of action below.

1. Creating a shared foundation and vision for open education

Developing a shared understanding and definition of open education and the value of OER is vital. This includes establishing a common agenda, vision, and process to guide collective action. To support this, the alliance can facilitate discussions around bigger challenges, such as creating quality and unified international standards, while also offering a safe space for candid discussions around contentious issues, such as the commercialisation of education.

2. Advocating for digital transformation in education through open education

Raising awareness is equally important. The alliance seeks to make OE, OER, open practices, and pedagogy more visible across Europe, while building a strong open education movement and community. Efforts can focus on training educators and policymakers to become effective advocates for change and amplifying the existing work of organisations already active in the field.

3. Influencing policy and strategy to bring education resources and processes relevant and up-to-date

Another key area involves influencing policy at international, national, and local levels. By positioning open education at the forefront of educational innovation, the alliance would aim to ensure that it becomes a strategic priority through increased policy action and alignment.

4. Advancing innovation and knowledge-sharing

The alliance should prioritise advancing innovation and knowledge exchange to connect, support, solve common problems, innovate, and inspire. This includes improving OER discoverability, tackling interoperability challenges, and effectively addressing the impact of emerging technological trends, such as AI, on open education. AI was especially mentioned many times as an obvious area of shared European interest. Note that this report does not go into how AI could affect OE or an alliance since it focusses on identifying needs. Central to this effort is the equitable distribution of knowledge and developing a knowledge hub to foster experimentation and incubation. In future, one could pursue joint projects and funding opportunities to strengthen collective impact and solve bigger problems together. We recommend that the alliance's role be primarily facilitative: stimulating, guiding, enabling, and advocating for change in access to knowledge through open education. The alliance should support a community, one made up of partners, experts, observers, and beneficiaries. It will be vital to give due attention to how this is organised.

Advancing and fostering the cultural shift towards openness at the international level requires the collaborative commitment of the diverse stakeholders that the alliance aims to bring together. Their efforts, grounded not only in the evidence-based benefits of open education but also driven by a shared dedication to its core values that education is a public good, will enable them to envision and build a more inclusive, transparent, and interconnected future, both within Europe and beyond. This dual approach is essential to

catalyse the profound cultural transformation needed to build on each other's progress for the common good, while respecting local priorities.

An international open education alliance could act as a central node to unite and empower existing efforts, providing the collective strength needed to influence policy, drive large-scale collaborations, and address systemic challenges that are simply beyond the reach of individual organisations. This unified approach has the potential to create a powerful, coordinated movement that is essential for building a truly open and equitable European educational ecosystem.

While the alliance's target audience will ultimately depend on its mandate, an international open education alliance should engage a wide spectrum of stakeholders, with the learner at the centre as the primary beneficiary. Members of the alliance, participants and observers will all have important roles to play, which need to be defined in a co-created future governance structure at the initiation of an alliance. The alliance should foster strategic partnerships with policymakers and funders on one side, and with a broader community offering practical, ground-level expertise on the other. The primary target group should include decision-makers at the highest levels, i.e. policymakers and funders at institutional, regional, national, and European levels who drive and implement systemic change by influencing legislation, funding, and broader educational agendas, and system change agents such as SURF in the Netherlands. Since commercial service providers are part of the transformative solution, they should, under certain circumstances, also be part of the alliance. Libraries can act as important intermediaries between policymakers and practitioners, if not service providers themselves, and universities and colleges are the ones with the experts and practitioners who can mobilise and implement change. New partnerships will need to be built and this will take time. In summary, by bringing diverse actors together through a new alliance that drives open education forward, a stronger movement can emerge, driving more action to place open education at the centre of Europe's educational transformation.

It is now to be determined as to whether there is an appetite for key organisations to pursue the path towards developing a European alliance for open education. SPARC Europe wishes to explore the potential further with those who share the vision of a European Alliance for Open Education.

9. ANNEXE

ANNEXE A Dutch expert questionnaire summary

Selected Dutch experts were asked to complete a short questionnaire of four questions before the interview. Answers were collected via an online form. Twelve of fourteen interviewees responded. Summaries and analyses of the data gathered are provided below in response to each question.

Npuls is the Dutch national transformation programme in tertiary education. It runs from 2023 until 2031 and includes all publicly funded tertiary educational institutions in The Netherlands. Below, the term “Dutch national programme” refers to it.

Question 1: Which of the following specific activities of the Dutch national programme cannot fully be realised by the programme only?

National programme Phase 2 activity	% agreement
1. Dealing with big tech and edtech - digital sovereignty. Acting together in conversations with suppliers.	100%
2. Standards for sharing open teaching materials.	92%
3. Ensuring collaborative agreements place public values above the interests of commercial parties.	83%
4. Agreeing on what constitutes a common, basic, knowledge sharing infrastructure.	75%
5. Legislation and regulation.	75%
6. Enhancing quality of education by learning and innovating together including removing barriers to enable more flexible use of educational offerings.	67%
7. Working together to formulate new forms and agreements for provision of ICT systems and digital education resources.	58%
8. Enabling transformation by creating new forms of governance, management, organization, and financing.	58%
9. Management and continuous development of teaching and learning infrastructures as well as collective (ICT) applications necessary for the	50%

new way of working across the entire education administrative chain (all systems and all processes).	
10. Designing and creating new digital facilities available for the entire sector.	50%
11. Digital literacy, including ability to use digital resources properly and safely.	33%
12. Opportunities to collaborate nationally and internationally on system, process and vision	8%

Analysis: There is widespread agreement that the transformation programme cannot fully realise many of its activities independently. Those activities constitute areas for international alliance collaboration. There is almost unanimous agreement that dealing with big tech and edtech and setting standards requires international cooperation. These are the top two priorities.

Question 2: Which of the following specific activities of the Dutch national programme cannot fully be realised by the programme on its own? Prioritise your choices by ticking the boxes with 8 being the most important. (boxes go from 0 to 8. With 12 respondents the max possible score = 96. Lowest possible score = 0)

Programme Area	Aggregate Score
AI and Data	85
Digital sector facilities	81
EdTech	79
XR	73
Digital Learning Resources	72
Agile organised education	65
Knowledge hub learning & innovation	64
Digital testing and development	63

Analysis: AI & data, digital sector facilities, and edtech are seen as the three most important programme areas for collaboration, followed by XR and digital learning resources. The lowest score is 67%, suggesting that all transformation programme areas benefit from international collaboration.

Question 3: Name other efforts or organizations you are aware of doing work in these areas.

In response, the following organisations were identified:

1. European University Information Systems organisation [EUNIS](#)
2. European Digital Education Hub [EDEH](#)
3. Hochschulforum Digitalisierung [HFD](#) (x2)
4. Collaboration of European National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) [GEANT](#)
5. [NRENS4EDUCATION](#) (this is a mailing list option of GEANT)
6. European Commission [EC](#)
7. European University Institute [EUI](#)
8. Placed at the centre of European cooperation, Cedefop aimed at improving vocational education and training (VET) through effective policy-making. [CEDEFOP](#)
9. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD](#)
10. Netherlands Initiative for Educational Research [NRO](#)
11. IT cooperative of education and research [SURF](#)
12. UK digital, data and technology agency focused on tertiary education, research and innovation [JISC](#)
13. Digivisio 2030 is a joint programme whose aim is to create a future for learning that benefits higher education institutions, learners and our society as a whole. [DIGIVISIO2030](#)
14. Kennisnet ensures that schools can use technology to improve the quality and accessibility of education and to manage security and ICT risks [Kennisnet](#)
15. United Nations for Education, Science & Culture Organization [UNESCO](#)
16. Actor facilitating connectivity between the National Research and Education Networks (RNIE), and enabler of the digital transformation processes of education, science, technology and innovation in Latin America and the Caribbean. [RedCLARA](#)
17. Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS) is a network of influential organisations committed to helping secure OA and OS infrastructure [SCOSS](#)
18. Non-profit organisation with a mission to promote open scholarship and improve discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility, and monitoring of data-driven research results globally. European e-infrastructure offers a diverse set of public services to accelerate the adoption of Open Science, and it is supported

by a network of experts placed in key national organisations across European countries, the National Open Access Desks [OpenAire](#).

19. Advancing Open Science in Europe [EOSC](#)

Analysis: Numerous other organisations work in the transformation programme’s areas of expertise. These organisations need to be evaluated for potential inclusion in an international alliance.

Question 4: The Dutch national programme is already engaged in some international collaborations including:

- *Development of standards and solutions for learning without barriers and continuous best education*
- *One reference interoperable architecture for barrier- free learning and digital sovereignty in public education*
- *Standards for describing and recognizing educational units - microcredentials*
- *Shared international platform for developing and sharing educational resources (e.g. Xerte)*
- *Connecting and promoting the learning culture in educational institutions (Teaching and Learning Centres)*
- *International Roundtable for Digital Transformation in Education (currently Germany, Finland and JISC are partners with NL)*
- *Other*

Which of these do you think can be the basis for an alliance?

Existing International Collaboration	% agreement as basis for an alliance
International Roundtable for Digital Transformation in Education (currently Germany, Finland and JISC are partners with NL)	75%
Shared international platform for developing and sharing educational resources (e.g. Xerte)	67%
One reference interoperable architecture for barrier- free learning and digital sovereignty in public education	58%
Development of standards and solutions for learning without barriers and continuous best education	58%

Standards for describing and recognizing educational units - microcredentials	50%
Connecting and promoting the learning culture in educational institutions (Teaching and Learning Centres)	42%
Other responses:	
Public private partnership	8%
Work with European Commission working groups, European federations of Education, employers and teachers. Alliances for VET education and higher education, such as Aurora Universities, Neth-ER, EFEE, EUNICS, Erasmus+ programme, Horizon, Nuffic, etc.	8%
Digital autonomy/sovereignty	8%
From my point of view, it's difficult to say, but there are many opportunities, and what do we emphasise on	8%

Analysis: There is good overall support for integrating existing collaborations into an international alliance. The International Roundtable for Digital Transformation in Education initiative is the most important.

ANNEXE B Dutch expert interviews summary

Fourteen Dutch experts were interviewed in June 2025—a template of eight questions guided all interviews, which took over an hour.

Analysis: Summaries and analyses of the data gathered are provided below in response to each question.

Question 1. Are there any Dutch national programme ambitions that can only or better be realised by working with others internationally?

International collaboration is needed for every goal and promise of the national programme. Learning without barriers entails inviting students from outside the country to learn from the Netherlands and supporting Dutch learners to learn from others outside the country. Borders of a country cannot be a barrier for learners. Education does not stop at borders.

Figure 2. National programme ambitions that can only or better be realised by working with others internationally

1. Addressing Big Tech and EdTech Market Power: To effectively counter the market dominance of large technology and education technology companies, national efforts must operate on a European or even global scale. National initiatives alone are insufficient to influence these influential international players. An international alliance provides a way of building market power on the demand side. A unified international alliance provides a strong foundation for negotiating terms and conditions on the use of learning materials and ensuring that public values are upheld in digital learning environments and agreements. An international alliance mitigates significant tech challenges to digital sovereignty by establishing alternative ways of sourcing infrastructure and services.

2. Facilitating the Sharing and Reuse of Learning Materials: Although there's a recognised need for infrastructure to share learning materials, the "why" and motivation for sharing aren't always clear to individual educators, directors, policymakers and national leaders. International collaboration can bolster the case for sharing. International materials for subjects like health care, nursing, IT, engineering, agriculture, and others that transcend national borders make flexible cross-border learning possible. Student mobility necessitates internationally available and reusable materials. Overcoming the inherent difficulty of sharing materials (even within an institution) becomes more feasible with international impetus and proven models of quality content that can be reused. An international alliance can build a common curriculum and share it. Ultimately, an international alliance can enhance how learning materials are developed, adopted, reused, and maintained.

3. Fostering a Culture of Openness and Collaboration: A significant transformation and cultural shift is required to fully realise national programme goals. Infrastructure and materials are important, but the culture shift entails a reframing of learning and a broader education concept. This change process requires the creation of a shared mindset based on a different way of looking at education. Openness, sharing, collaboration, and connecting are integral to this new mindset. Making this culture shift requires addressing fear of sharing, a shift to finding, reusing and maintaining quality resources, learning new pedagogical practices, and changing systems of reward and recognition. The culture shift entails working as a network of institutions and envisioning what a field or discipline looks like, but can only be achieved by collective work as a network. An international alliance brings together collective efforts toward this culture shift, providing a powerful platform for "learning together," exchanging good practices, and gaining a broader perspective on successes and challenges. The combined efforts of international initiatives can generate the "why" of this new way of learning, along with associated stories and motivations that create a shared mindset among educators, directors, and policymakers, moving from individual efforts to a unified movement.

4. Building and Connecting Digital Infrastructure: While the Dutch national programme has the capacity to develop national infrastructure, collaborating internationally would create a stronger, more interconnected system. A shared European-wide technical vision, a set of frameworks for connecting what we do with what they do, and an ecosystem process for sharing and linking infrastructure would help enable flexible learning and student mobility across countries. Interoperable infrastructures for working with and sharing learning materials, credentials, student IDs, digital wallets, personalised learning pathways, and community learning are needed. Institutional digital infrastructures and those used directly by educators must be included. Sharing existing infrastructure, learning from the successes and pitfalls of others, and actively linking various national infrastructures benefit all. An international alliance platform for exchanging knowledge is needed to enable this process.

5. Agreeing on Standards and Interoperability: Achieving seamless learning without borders, a key Dutch national programme ambition, fundamentally relies on international standardisation. This includes agreeing on standards for data exchange, digital wallets, student IDs, credentials, skills and learning outcomes, and personalised learning pathways. Standardisation includes agreeing collectively on what open means, encompassing concepts like the commons, technical standards (e.g. FAIR), and machine readability. Standards and systems for sharing knowledge need to be agreed on. While national standards are a starting point, validating and adapting them to international needs and cultures is vital. Collectively building an open education European interoperability framework provides the opportunity to move beyond national "our standards" to a shared, internationally recognised approach. An international alliance offers the means for creating and implementing shared European standards.

6. Influencing International Policy and Legislation: For higher education, impacting policies and legislation at the European level necessitates an international alliance. A strong, collective agenda from multiple countries is needed to effectively influence these broader discussions and ensure that the culture shift associated with this new vision of education is supported by policy and legislation, including those that foster learning without barriers, student and labour mobility, international standards, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of open practices. An international alliance provides a means for sharing and learning from existing policy and collectively drafting new policy. Existing successful research and open science policies from across the alliance can provide a useful model to learn from. An international alliance could effectively influence legislation and policy at the European level necessary in areas of technical changes such as AI and its impact on education.

7. Promoting Recognition and Reward for Open Practices: A significant barrier to wider adoption of open practices is the lack of formal recognition and reward for teaching staff and faculty who engage in open work, collaboration, and sharing. An international ambition or mechanism for recognising open contributions, such as open textbooks, would be a significant step forward. Academic career development within and across institutions must include recognition of open work, highlighting the benefits of reuse and wider impact. An international alliance could establish precedents for appointing full professors based on their impact in open scholarship, fostering a system-wide change that values contributions beyond traditional research outputs.

8. Strategic Resource Allocation and Sustainability: While national funding is important, international alliances can provide access to broader funding landscapes and support the longevity of open infrastructure initiatives that often struggle with project-based financing. In some countries, ministerial interest in open education has waned. An international alliance can reignite ministerial interest. By working together, countries can ensure a more efficient and impactful use of public money, creating a sustainable ecosystem for open education and open science.

Ultimately, for the Dutch national programme to achieve its comprehensive goals, international collaboration is not just beneficial but essential.

Question 2: The Dutch national programme is aiming for transformative change in education. Are you aware of other international initiatives seeking similar transformative change?

The national programme is not alone in its pursuit of transformative change in education. However, there's a "blind spot" regarding who else is doing similar transformative work, highlighting a need for better international networking and knowledge sharing. Several international initiatives were identified who are working towards similar goals, including:

1. [Digivisio](#) (Finland): This initiative is from CSC—IT Center for Science, a Finnish centre of expertise in information technology owned by the Finnish state and higher education institutions. Digivisio seeks to enable flexible study opportunities across all Finnish higher education institutions, irrespective of organisational boundaries, and is strongly supported by the Ministry of Science and Culture.
2. [KLASCement](#) (Belgium): The Educational Resources Network KlasCement is managed by the Division of Communication of the Department of Education and Training. While initially a transformative programme, KlasCement is now more embedded as a normal, operational digital education platform. It focuses on teachers sharing open educational resources (OER) for various educational levels.

3. [NDLA](#) (Norway): The Norwegian Digital Learning Arena (NDLA) is Norway's leading producer of digital learning resources for upper secondary education. Our platform consists of 20,000 learning resources covering 141 examination subjects. The Norwegian Digital Learning Arena focuses on providing open educational resources for upper secondary education.
4. [Hochschulforum Digitalisierung](#) (HFD) (Germany): Founded in 2014, the Hochschulforum Digitalisierung is a joint initiative of the Stifterverband, the CHE Centre for Higher Education and the German Rectors' Conference (HRK). It is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). A nationwide think-&-do tank, the Hochschulforum Digitalisierung (HFD) brings together a broad community around digitalisation in teaching and learning, makes developments visible, and tests innovative solutions. To this end, stakeholders from universities, politics, business and society are networked, accompanied and advised. This group is good at strategy but does not have executive power for infrastructure development. The federation of states creates challenges.
5. [WirLernenOnline](#) (Germany): This German initiative aims to be a search engine and community for open educational materials (OER), focusing on curated, quality-checked content, and leveraging AI for metadata generation. WirLernenOnline is a joint project of Wikimedia Deutschland eV and edu-sharing.net, funded as part of a COVID-19 emergency aid programme of the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)
6. [Technische Informationsbibliothek](#) (TIB) (Germany) Axel Klinger is the technical coordinator of the Lower Saxony OER portal <https://twillo.de> and the international OER Search Index <https://oersi.org>, which focuses on OER in higher education. They are bringing together distributed heterogeneous repositories to harmonise metadata and make them searchable in one place, with the option to integrate the OERSI search into institutional websites.
7. [JISC](#) (UK): JISC is a UK digital, data and technology agency focused on tertiary education, research and innovation. Their vision is to lead the UK tertiary education, research and innovation sectors to be pioneers in using digital technology and data. Most of their funding comes from UK higher education and further education funding bodies, with additional support coming from membership subscriptions from higher education institutions (UK-wide) and further education institutions (in England only). JISC is extensively involved in digital transformation in UK higher education, offering frameworks and guidance. While open education used to be high on their agenda, it is less so now. They focus on leadership, investment, infrastructure, digital skills, and content. They are also researching digital challenges in transnational education. JISC has great frameworks but lacks money.

8. [European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan](#) (DG EAC, DG Connect): The EC has a strong focus on digital education, aiming to foster a high-performing digital education ecosystem and enhance digital skills. They support infrastructure development through multiple Directorates-General and are working on a European Digital Education Hub to facilitate cross-sectoral exchange and strategic collaboration
9. [Aurora University Alliance](#): Aurora was formed in 2016 as a consortium of research-intensive universities deeply committed to the social impact of their activities and with a history of engagement with their communities. As nine universities working together, they aim to harness their academic excellence to influence societal change through research and educational activities – and ultimately to contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. The nine universities are: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, University of Iceland, University of Duisburg-Essen, University Federico II of Naples, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Universität Innsbruck, Palacký University Olomouc, Copenhagen Business School, Université Paris-Est Créteil. These university alliances are also working towards "studying without borders," though their focus is often more on student mobility and social benefits like SDGs, rather than digital infrastructure.
10. [UNESCO](#): UNESCO actively promotes Open Education through policy papers, although its documents are not always widely implemented.
11. [OAPEN](#) (Netherlands): OAPEN promotes and supports the transition to open access for academic books by providing open infrastructure services to stakeholders in scholarly communication. OAPEN works with publishers to build a quality-controlled collection of open access books and provides services for publishers, libraries, and research funders in hosting, deposit, quality assurance, dissemination, and digital preservation. OAPEN aligns with the broader open science movement.
12. [XERTE](#) (Aperero): Xerte is open-source software for authoring learning objects. It was developed by the University of Nottingham in the UK and is free to download from the Xerte Community website. Xerte is more than just an online e-learning authoring and delivery tool—it's a community-driven project, providing educators with a simple, accessible, and robust solution for creating rich and interactive content. Xerte is a software project of the Aperero Foundation, a global non-profit advancing open source software in the service of higher education.
13. [NORDUnet](#) (Nordic) is a collaboration of National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) of five Nordic countries: Denmark (DeiC), Iceland (RHnet), Norway (Uninett), Sweden (SUNET), and Finland (Funet). Since 1980, NORDUnet has operated a world-class network and e-infrastructure service for the Nordic research and education community. The five NRENs develop and manage the national research network

infrastructures, connecting more than 400 research & education institutions with more than 1.2 million users.

14. [SPARC Europe](#) is one of Europe's key and long-standing voices advocating for unfettered access to research and education. SPARC Europe is working to make European education and research open by default and is very active in Open Access, Open FAIR/Data, Open Education, and sustaining open. SPARC Europe has established a European Network of Open Education Librarians (ENOEL). ENOEL is a community of European academics who share educational values and advocate for Open Education (OE). Established in 2018, the network encourages and facilitates the exchange of ideas with peers and values learning from one another to drive Open Education possibilities forward.
15. [Open Education Global](#) (OEGlobal) is a member-based, global, non-profit supporting the development and use of open education around the world to:
 - Expand access to education, enabling every person on earth to access and contribute
 - improve the quality of education
 - make education more affordable
 - improve student success
 - foster collaboration and sharing through co-creation of education materials and the freedom to use, customise, improve and redistribute them
 - generate pedagogical innovation using the collaborative, interactive culture of the Internet
 - foster international partnerships and a global participatory culture of learning, creating, sharing and cooperation

While these initiatives have similar goals, they vary in scope, focus, and levels of strategic integration. However, there are ample opportunities for collaboration around areas of common interest.

Different countries and institutions operate with different organisational logics, governance structures, and conceptions of roles. The Dutch national programme needs to find ways to bridge these differences to facilitate true international collaboration.

One important consideration is that “open” is not just a technological concept but also a culture and way of thinking. Transforming education requires addressing this cultural shift, which is a common challenge across all initiatives.

3. What Dutch national programme challenges / opportunities can only or better be realized through collective international action?

The programme faces several challenges and opportunities that can only be fully realised through collective international action.

1. **Overcoming National Silos and Fostering Collective Thinking:** The Dutch national programme is a collective effort, but truly transformative change requires moving beyond institutional, local, and even national thinking to a broader European or international perspective. A fragmented approach weakens overall impact. Speaking from a collective international position increases influence, credibility, and power in discussions with governments, funders, and publishers. Collective effort enables the development of a shared ecosystem for managing, accessing, and reusing digital learning resources, fostering an "open mindset" and culture where sharing is the norm. It also facilitates knowledge exchange of good practices, learning from successes and pitfalls, and avoiding redundant efforts across countries. While local efforts are important, the fundamental "mindset shift" required for actual transformative change in education is a universal challenge. International collaboration, viewed as a "learning community approach," can provide support, shared stories, and validation for institutions and individuals striving to change deeply ingrained practices and ensure recognition and reward for open work.
2. **Influencing Publishers and Big Tech:** Individual institutions or even national collectives hold limited sway over powerful international publishers and big tech companies. A European or international collective voice, representing many universities, carries significantly more weight in negotiating agreements (e.g. terms and conditions for learning materials, data protection, privacy, etc.). This collective strength is essential to bring public values back into the control of learning materials and enable digital sovereignty. There is a growing need for public/private approaches built around public values. While "open" can be challenging for commercial partners, focusing on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles for educational resources may offer a more pragmatic route to achieving open.
3. **Establishing and Adopting International Standards:** The seamless exchange of learning materials, student credentials (like micro-credentials), digital identities, and data (grades, metadata, student information systems) requires common international standards. While national standards can be a starting point, they must be validated and adapted for international applicability. Cross-border student

mobility and standard curricula highlight the urgent need for interoperable solutions that national systems alone cannot provide. Given its rapid evolution and global reach, AI development and its ethical, responsible use in education also necessitate international agreement on standards and practices.

4. **Shifting Teaching Culture and Adapting to Rapid Change:** The fundamental shift in teaching from traditional methods to open practices (and now AI) is a monumental cultural change. Open is not just about learning materials; it is more cross-cutting, including practices, pedagogies, and policies. This transformation is occurring at a fast pace and presents common challenges across countries. International collaboration allows for shared learning, research, and development of best practices for supporting this culture change. Culture change also includes a learning without borders approach to education. Learning, supporting student and labour mobility requires international frameworks for skills and competencies.
5. **Securing Funding and Sustainable Infrastructure:** A collective international approach and roadmap can advocate for more substantial and sustained funding for shared digital infrastructure that benefits all participating institutions.
6. **Harmonising Policies and Practices:** Duplication of efforts occurs when countries develop policies in isolation. International collaboration, potentially through a European committee, can lead to more unified policies, for example, regarding public values in sharing knowledge or AI agreements for learning materials.

The Dutch national programme's journey towards transformative educational change is inherently linked to its ability to act collectively on an international stage. This not only amplifies its voice and influence but also enables the development of shared infrastructure, standards, and cultural shifts necessary for a truly borderless and equitable learning environment.

4. What should the remit (mandate and goal) of an international open education alliance be?

An international open education alliance should have a comprehensive mandate focused on accelerating digital transformation in education through collective action, shared standards, and a unified vision, transcending national boundaries. Its core goals and activities should include:

Mandate and Goals:

1. Stimulating Innovation and Digital Transition
 - Accelerate innovation: Facilitate the rapid adoption of digital learning materials and pedagogical advancements across Europe.
 - Knowledge sharing: Create mechanisms for partners to exchange experiences, best practices, and insights to speed up the digital transition process, learning from both successes and pitfalls.
2. Standardisation and Interoperability
 - Enable seamless exchange: Establish and promote international standards for metadata sets, digital identities (e.g. student IDs, digital wallets), and learning material properties to ensure discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of open educational content. Make open education more trackable (e.g. track how OER are being used). This includes aligning with broader European technical standards.
 - Connect infrastructures: Work towards connecting national and institutional infrastructures and services to create a more integrated and accessible European ecosystem for open education. Make it easy for institutions to adopt open education within their existing IT infrastructures. Ensure open is available in the environment where students and teachers are.
3. Unified Understanding and Value Proposition of Open Education
 - Define "open": Develop a shared understanding and common definition of "open education" among all stakeholders, clarifying its values and benefits. Ensure everyone sees it the same way, understands the culture of an open mindset, and understands the value.
 - Promote public values: Ground the alliance's work in public values, making open education and its benefits tangible and appealing to a broad audience, including board members, policymakers and especially students and teachers.

- Highlight benefits: Showcase how open education can improve the quality of education and provide economic benefits for students, institutions and the labour market.
4. Collective Advocacy and Market Power
- Stronger voice: Act as a collective voice for the education sector to influence governments, policymakers (e.g. the European Commission), and powerful international publishers. Establish shared goals. This collective stance is crucial for negotiating favourable agreements on terms and conditions for learning materials and infrastructures. It is also key for advocating for changes in national and European funding structures, rules, and regulations in the way of openness. Create market power by having the alliance speak on behalf of participating organisations.
 - Influence funding: Work to shape future European funding calls and research programmes on open education. Create a stronger voice and greater impact by pooling funding.
5. Facilitating Collaboration and Community Building
- Bridging "islands": Bring together diverse stakeholders – teachers, support staff, management, librarians, NRENs, national policy bodies, and institutions – who currently operate in silos but face similar challenges and share common questions. Create and connect nodes across countries.
 - Common agenda: Establish a common agenda with shared priorities to foster collaborative efforts rather than redundant individual initiatives. Ensure the common agenda has unique selling points to not duplicate other efforts. Identify common needs across efforts and prioritise them to focus collective effort. Consider pooling and targeting funding to address common needs.
 - Linking individuals and organisations: Create "linking pins" and platforms to facilitate exchange between different groups and enable the formation of working groups. The alliance should work with umbrella organisations to amplify its reach and power.
 - Learning community approach: Promote a "learning together" ethos, fostering social change and a shared "open mindset" across institutions and countries.
 - Enlarge open content, collections, and credentials based on open.

6. Capacity Building and Awareness Raising

- Support for teachers: Address the critical challenge of changing teaching practices by providing professional development, resources, and incentives (e.g. recognition, rewards, time allocation) for educators to engage in open practices.
- Awareness beyond the "converted": Raise awareness about the benefits and practicalities of open education for all stakeholders, including institutional boards, ministries, and political parties, reframing "open" as a strategic rather than just a technical or cost-saving issue.
- Data-driven decision making: Collect data on educator needs, common material usage, and purchasing patterns to identify high-impact areas for developing open alternatives and stimulating OER reuse.

7. Scope and Role

Inclusive scope: While initial efforts focus on universities of applied science and research universities, the mandate could eventually extend to primary and secondary education for a more holistic, transformative impact.

- Public values at core: The alliance's efforts should centre on promoting public values in education, ensuring that decisions about learning materials prioritise learners' best interests.
- Strategic approach to "open": While the ultimate goal is openness, the alliance should explore pragmatic pathways to openness, especially when engaging with commercial entities or in contexts where complete openness is challenging.
- Lifelong learning: The mandate should include open lifelong learning offerings, providing flexible learning pathways and credentials.

Role as Facilitator, Not Implementer:

- The alliance should be primarily facilitative: stimulating, guiding, enabling, and advocating, rather than directly implementing solutions for individual institutions or countries. It should add to, rather than duplicate, national initiatives.

5. Who should the alliance serve? Who should be the primary audience? Should there be limits on who can be part of such an alliance? (e.g. can Big Tech, EdTech, and publishers participate? Institutions? System change agents like Npuls or SURF who are not academic institutions but have a system-wide mandate?)

An international open education alliance should serve a broad range of stakeholders, clearly focusing on the learner as the ultimate beneficiary.

The primary audience is those in positions of influence who drive and implement systemic change.

Ministry and educational leadership at the same table is not enough. The alliance must also include those directly involved in the practical aspects of education. Talking with education rather than about education is essential. The alliance is seen as a means for making that discussion possible. To ensure student and teacher pain points are well understood, they may need to be not only alliance beneficiaries but its participants. Alliance activities need to address all levels: students, educators, middle management, senior leaders, institutions, and national, and international initiatives.

The alliance should be strategic about who is "at the table." Limits to participation need to be defined. Adherence to and active contribution to public values is seen as a guiding principle for membership. The alliance needs to differentiate members from observers, partners, and beneficiaries. The alliance is seen as bringing together national efforts, so those who can speak about open education at a national level are seen as important voices at the table.

Who the Alliance Should Serve (Beneficiaries)

- **Learners (Students):** As the most important target group, students are the ultimate beneficiaries. The alliance should ensure there is a collective understanding of student requirements. The alliance can address "pain points" to improve their learning experience and ensure satisfied learners.
- **Teachers/Educators:** As the implementers of open education practices, they are critical beneficiaries, needing support, resources, and recognition for their efforts. They are often perceived as the "hardest to change." The alliance should work together to fully understand teachers' challenges in their daily lives and work with them on the change models. Open education needs to move from the libraries to the educators themselves. The alliance can work to ensure shared approaches to open pedagogies, including the redesign of entire programmes to be open. Roadmaps for how to do this could be helpful from the alliance, especially if they could be adapted to a specific context or culture.

- Institutions: The alliance is seen as creating a movement where all institutions act together. The alliance can address institutional legal, teaching, and IT technical issues, especially those around which there is collective institutional will.
- Labour Market and Society: The alliance's efforts should ultimately benefit the labour market by ensuring learners acquire in-demand skills (applied skills vs. theoretical knowledge) and society by fostering innovation and addressing societal challenges. Ultimately, the beneficiaries are all those who learn in the education system and anyone who provides services.

Who should Be the Primary Audience (for driving change)

The primary audience for the alliance's communication and influence should be those who can enact broad, systemic change:

- Ministries and Policymakers: At national and European levels, as well as policy advisors to institutions. These are the key players for influencing legislation, funding, and broader educational agendas.
- Board Members and Institutional Leadership: These individuals make strategic decisions regarding finance, quality, and institutional direction. The alliance needs to effectively communicate the value proposition of open education to them and engage them in making commitments.
- Policy advisors on internationalisation: Individuals focused on cross-border educational strategies within institutions.
- System change agents (e.g. Npuls, SURF, Kennisnet, NRENs): These organisations should be key members as they have a system-wide mandate, making them crucial partners for infrastructure and service development. They are essential partners in implementing policies and providing technical expertise. They have the collective mandate to support digital transformation. They can also serve as national nodes for broader European collaboration.
- IT Professionals: Critical for building and maintaining the necessary digital infrastructure, managing data (e.g. analytics, ownership), and addressing technical and legal issues related to sharing and interoperability.

The alliance should be strategic about who is "at the table" as a member (with voting power) versus who are beneficiaries or partners for specific discussions. The guiding principle for membership should be adherence to and active contribution towards public values. The alliance should seek to identify and engage peers in other countries leading national digital transformation or open education efforts, understanding that organisational structures vary significantly between nations. This includes communities of policymakers, ICT architects, and managers working on digital transformation at the institutional level.

Strong Candidates for Membership/Collaboration

- Educational Institutions (Universities, Universities of Applied Sciences, Vocational Training Schools): Their direct involvement is crucial, providing insights into practical needs and challenges.
- System change agents/National Bodies:
 - Npuls (Netherlands) and SURF (Netherlands) are current leaders in comprehensive digital transformation and open education.
 - CSC / Digivisio 2030 (Finland): Admired for its centralised approach and focus on open.fi platform.
 - LaDoc (Sweden): Noted for its unified student information system and strong national alignment.
 - JISC (UK): Acknowledged for its extensive frameworks in digital transformation, even if open education isn't currently its highest priority.
 - National Research and Education Networks (NRENs): These networks have existing infrastructure and expertise and can serve as national nodes for broader international collaboration.
- International Organisations:
 - UNESCO: Highly active in promoting open education through policy and global initiatives (e.g. OER Recommendation, Global Education Coalition). Essential for its worldwide reach and normative work.
 - Research Data Alliance (RDA): Admired for its work in open data standards and its ability to influence at the EU Commission level, even with individual members.
 - EUA (European University Association) and LERU (League of European Research Universities): Influential university associations, particularly in Open Science, with established networks for policy engagement and sharing best practices.
 - OAPEN: For its focus on open access textbooks and content.
 - European Federations of Employers/Teachers: To ensure alignment with labour market needs and teacher perspectives.
- Societal Organisations: Groups focused on specific sectors (e.g. green energy, healthcare) that need highly skilled staff and can articulate labour market demands.
- Individuals: Like RDA, individual membership can open doors at higher levels (e.g. EC). Peer communities (policymakers, architects) should be fostered. The alliance should primarily engage through umbrella organisations to maximise collective power.
- Activists: Especially those championing public values in education.

Participation of Commercial Entities (Big Tech, EdTech, Publishers)

- Not as Full Voting Members: There's a strong preference to exclude Big Tech, EdTech, and publishers from full voting membership due to their inherent profit-driven models, which can conflict with the public values of open education.
- As Partners for Specific Discussions: They should be invited to the table for strategic discussions where their market power, technical knowledge, or existing infrastructure is relevant, particularly concerning standards, interoperability, and data use.
- The alliance should clearly define its negotiables and non-negotiables beforehand, setting conditions for their participation that ensure alignment with public values and the alliance's goals. The aim is to leverage their capabilities to serve the public education agenda, not to be absorbed into their agenda and ecosystems.
- Outsourcing vs. Insourcing: The alliance could aim to build its own "ecosystem" to counter the trend of more education services, including data and content, being "sucked into" publishers and big tech. It does not desire models where institutions and learners do not have control.

Other Stakeholders for Specific Roles

- Government (Legal/Regulation): This is important for understanding legal frameworks, compliance, and advocating for regulatory changes.
- Project Managers, Change Managers, HR, Library Staff (curation, metadata) and Information Managers are essential for the practical implementation of initiatives within institutions. However, their direct involvement at the international alliance level might be through national entities that aggregate their needs.
- Researchers: Especially those focused on learning opportunities and related fields.

The alliance's success will depend on its ability to forge a powerful, unified collective that prioritises public values and learner well-being, while strategically engaging all necessary parties to achieve its transformative goals.

6. What should the alliance not focus on?

An international open education alliance should avoid focusing on areas that are primarily the domain of individual institutions or that could hinder transformative change already underway. It should also avoid being a top-down, prescriptive body that disregards institutional autonomy.

Areas to avoid

- **Short-term, Tactical Learning:** The alliance shouldn't concentrate on short-term learning goals solely for immediate placement, but rather on overarching structures aligned with European values that promote long-term, systemic transformation.
- **Interfering with Institutional Identity or Autonomy:** The alliance must not undermine or threaten the unique identity of individual institutions. Standardisation efforts, while important, should not be implemented in a way that feels forced or compromises institutional sovereignty. It's crucial to ensure members are convinced, not forced, to adopt changes.
- **Direct Intervention in Primary Institutional Activities:** The core focus should not be on institutions' primary activities, such as teaching and valorisation.
- **Direct Support/Interference with Individual Teachers:** While supporting teachers is vital, the alliance shouldn't directly intervene with individual educators' day-to-day practices. Support should be channelled through national and institutional structures.
- **Solely Technical Infrastructure Investment:** The alliance's IT focus shouldn't be limited to simply investing in infrastructure. Instead, it should concentrate on the "how-to" of implementing and utilising that infrastructure effectively to drive change.
- **Operating as a Project Organisation:** The alliance's remit should not be that of a temporary project-based entity. Its goal is transformation and cultural change, requiring a long-term commitment and a focus on systemic shifts rather than isolated projects.
- **Dictating Centralised Systems to Autonomous Institutions:** While collective action is important, the alliance shouldn't attempt to impose a single, consolidated identity (e.g. a "University of Netherlands" concept) or fully centralised student information systems if it goes against the high level of autonomy institutions cherish.

By avoiding these pitfalls, an international open education alliance can maintain focus on its transformative goals, respect institutional independence, and foster genuine, collaborative change.

7. What organizations do you admire as leaders in this work, either international or regional, national or local in scope? Who would you invite to be part of an international alliance?

Admiration was expressed for:

1. [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA)
2. [League of European Research Universities](#) (LERU)
3. Finland [Opin.fi](#) System wide shared platform for finding open study courses available across 37 institutions, all in one place. You can familiarise yourself with the study opportunities of Finnish higher education institutions, browse and compare, choose and learn – anytime, anywhere, whether you are in Finland or abroad. You can find Finnish, Swedish and English studies as both contact teaching and distance learning. Whether you are looking for a webinar, podcast or more comprehensive education, Opin.fi puts learning opportunities at your fingertips.
4. Sweden [LaDok](#) shares one student information system and one overall overarching view of students. Unheard of in the Netherlands.
5. Efforts that are not student-driven but macroeconomic productivity, labour market, and nationally driven.
6. Efforts that yield more access and more choice.
7. The way the four Scandinavian countries work together. Seems very aligned with big transitional challenges.
8. Theory on system change (Rotterdam)
9. European Federations' pursuit of programmes for digital transformation and lifelong learning.
10. Open Science - need to learn from organisations and institutions doing Open Science.

8. Is there anything else you'd like to share with us about such an international open education alliance?

An international open education alliance should be a transformative and cultural change organisation, not merely a project-based one. Its success hinges on strategic focus, concrete results, and broad collaboration that includes practitioners and respects diverse contexts.

Key considerations for the alliance

1. **Catalyst for National Initiatives:** The alliance can serve as a crucial "connecting tissue" for national open education initiatives. By fostering collaboration and sharing best practices, it can identify emerging trends, connect like-minded individuals and organisations, and accelerate the digital transition across Europe and beyond. Organisations like OEGlobal and ALT (from the UK) are vital for bringing in the practitioner and community perspective.
2. **Focus on "How-To" for Infrastructure and Change:** The alliance should move beyond simply advocating for infrastructure investment. Its primary focus should be on the "how-to"—providing guidance, methodologies, and blueprints for implementing open education, including effectively using digital tools and infrastructure. This includes sharing lifecycle management models for Open Educational Resources (OER) and strategies for integrating OER into course design.
3. **Concrete Results and Pilot Approach:** To maintain credibility and avoid becoming "a big group of people talking but no results," the alliance must prioritise presenting concrete, tangible results. A smart approach would be to start small with pilot projects, learn from them, and then scale up successful initiatives.
4. **Standardisation and Interoperability:** A key initial focus should be on developing and promoting stable standards for exchanging digital data and content for reuse. This is an area where even publishers might be agreeable, as stability benefits all. While pedagogy may vary across cultures, the underlying standards for content exchange can be universal.
5. **Addressing Data and Content Ownership in the AI Era:** With the rise of AI, the alliance must tackle critical issues like the ownership of data and content, particularly teacher copyright, and the transfer of ownership to publishers. There's a concern that AI will profit from open content without proper mechanisms. The alliance needs to explore new models to ensure students control their own data and to protect content from being "sucked into" commercial ecosystems.
6. **Scope of "Open": Open vs. FAIR vs. Broader Transformation:**
 - There's an ongoing discussion about whether the alliance should focus on "open" or embrace a broader "FAIR" (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) approach, which might be more palatable for certain stakeholders and commercial partners.

- The alliance should focus on open pedagogy in addition to open learning materials, as this directly benefits students and drives deeper change.
 - It should also align with broader "use cases for interoperability" identified by the European Commission, particularly those related to managing educational resources, where NRENs can play a crucial role.
7. **Global vs. European Scope:** While a strong European focus is important given existing guidelines and initiatives (like EduGenAI and the Union of Skills program), there's a strong argument for the added value of expanding more broadly to include global perspectives. This allows for learning from diverse contexts, addressing global challenges (e.g. how micro-credentials compare across continents), and ensuring inclusivity, particularly from the Global South. However, this must be done credibly, unlike some past initiatives that genuinely failed to involve the Global South.
 8. **Backbone Organisation and Phased Approach:**
 - The alliance needs a "backbone organisation" with standing and reputation to initiate and lead the effort, similar to OA2020. This organisation would initially be prominent, but as the alliance gains traction, it should gradually move to the background, allowing for broader representation and "in-sourcing" from diverse global regions.
 - Avoid the pitfall of endless discussions; instead, build relationships iteratively and target conversations with key stakeholders who can make change.
 9. **Addressing Specific Sectors (VET):** There's a notable gap in vocational education and training (VET) regarding open education and open science initiatives. The alliance should consider how to engage VET colleges, which often operate regionally and have different research practices, by highlighting practical benefits to students (e.g. through micro-credentials and badges).

In essence, the international open education alliance needs to be a strategic, results-driven, and culturally sensitive force that empowers national initiatives, champions public values in the face of commercial pressures, and continually adapts to the evolving digital and AI landscape in education.

ANNEXE C International stakeholder interviews summary

Fourteen international stakeholders were interviewed in August 2025—a template of eight questions guided all interviews, which took over an hour.

Analysis: Summaries and analyses of the data gathered are provided below in response to each question.

1. What advantages do you see in such an Alliance?

There are several key advantages of an international open education alliance, focusing on its potential to foster collaboration, influence policy, and address systemic challenges in a unified manner.

Policy and Influence

An international alliance can unify open education across Europe and exert significant influence on policy at a European level, a role that individual institutions or even national groups cannot effectively perform. By speaking with a collective voice, the alliance can engage with and even bypass governments, advocating for policies that encourage sharing and support open education. This collective power is essential for negotiating with powerful entities like publishers and big EdTech companies, who, with their economies of scale, threaten institutional autonomy and digital sovereignty. The alliance can act as an intermediary consortium to set the direction of education in the age of AI. It aligns well with the priorities of the European Commission, which is actively seeking a European model for digital sovereignty to counter U.S. dominance.

Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange

The alliance would serve as a vital network for information and knowledge exchange, allowing different countries and institutions to learn from each other's digital strategies and policy approaches. This is particularly beneficial for sharing successful practices in embedding Open Educational Resources (OER) into curriculum design and delivery. An alliance focused on the practical application of OER can overcome barriers and show tangible benefits, moving beyond simple advocacy. It provides a focal point for support that has previously been fragmented, helping to break down silos and encouraging a unified, rather than duplicated, approach to shared challenges. An alliance can help institutional leaders think about the sector instead of just the institution.

Standardization and Technical Interoperability

A key advantage lies in the ability to collaborate on common standards and interoperability frameworks. Given the current fragmented systems, an alliance can lead the effort to pilot, test, and implement interoperable frameworks that allow different systems to work together seamlessly. This includes setting standards for open licensing, metadata, and accessibility, which are currently being developed in isolation. This is essential for scaling up pockets of success and enabling the easy discovery, adaptation, and translation of OER. The alliance can also take the lead in addressing the responsible use of AI in this context, leveraging it to overcome technical barriers while working within clear guardrails.

Global and Cultural Relevance

An international alliance provides a European focal point for open education, offering an alternative to the North American-centric view often associated with organisations like Creative Commons. It can promote a unique European approach to education that embraces the region's diversity while working toward unification. This platform can also strengthen the narrative of the Global North supporting the Global South and re-energize the conversation around open education by making its advantages visible and tangible.

2. What disadvantages do you see in an Alliance?

There are several potential disadvantages to an international open education alliance, primarily centred on challenges related to bureaucracy, coordination, and sustainability.

Lack of Clear Mandate and Focus

One of the most significant risks is that the alliance will not have a clearly defined mandate and will try to be "everything for everyone," leading to a lack of focus. It's crucial for the alliance to identify its niche and avoid simply adding another fragmented organization to an already crowded landscape. It must work to unite existing efforts rather than duplicating them.

Slow Progress and Coordination Challenges

The international nature of the alliance, with its broad audience and diverse perspectives, can make it difficult to move quickly. Coordinating a wide variety of stakeholders, all with different national contexts, can slow down progress and make it challenging to reach a shared understanding or agreement. Differences in opinion can also mean that a consensus reached at the alliance level may not translate to support at the national level.

Sustainability and Engagement

Transformation initiatives require a long-term commitment, but many organisations rely on short-term, project-based funding, which raises questions about the alliance's sustainability. The level of effort required to engage with special interest groups and working groups can be demanding, and people's involvement may fluctuate over time. To counter this, the alliance needs a clear mission and specific, time-phased objectives to maintain a sense of urgency and avoid becoming a "talking shop." It also needs compelling narratives and simple, easily available data to demonstrate its value and secure buy-in from new participants.

3. What should the remit (mandate and goal) of an international open education alliance be, one that others do not provide?

An international open education alliance, particularly one with a European focus, should fill a unique gap by acting as a central policy advocate and knowledge hub that supports the practical application of open education. Its core remit should not be to duplicate the work of existing organisations but to unite and strengthen them.

Mandate and Goals

The alliance's mandate should be informed by a needs assessment to ensure its focus is on high-impact areas. Key goals should include:

- **Policy Advocacy:** The alliance should influence policy at the European level, advocating for open education and addressing issues like digital sovereignty against US dominance in big tech. It can lobby governments and ministries to align their policies with the values of open education, especially when materials are funded by taxpayers.
- **Shaping a European Approach to Open Education:** A core goal should be to work toward a common European understanding, definition, and process for open education, which is currently lacking. It should show how open education can enable and facilitate all the goals shaping the future of teaching. It should show how open education is part of the DNA of higher education. This would involve overcoming legal and systemic obstacles that hold back European ambitions.
- **Connection to Broader Initiatives:** The alliance should explicitly link open education to major European and global priorities, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Council Recommendation on micro-credentialing and lifelong learning. This connection gives the alliance a powerful narrative for collaboration and shows how open education contributes to a more sustainable and equitable world, not just in formal academic communities, but for everyone.

- **Practical Implementation:** The alliance should move beyond advocacy to focus on the practice of open education. This includes investigating and sharing best practices for:
 - **Experimentation** with tools, technologies and new models, particularly around open teaching.
 - **Quality and Standards:** Promoting consistent standards for OER usage, identification, and utilization. This includes discoverability of OER (good quality, right for the context, easy adoption, substitution of commercial). What is being used, how it is being used, and challenges around use need to be tracked. This would involve coordinated engagement on standards, funding, and mandates, helping to create unified standards that individual countries lack.
 - **Vocational and Work-based Training:** Addressing the unique needs of vocational and further education, which have largely been overlooked in the open education movement.
 - **Curriculum Design:** Demonstrating how OER can be successfully integrated into curriculum design to improve teaching and facilitate future-ready education.
 - **Practices:** Shift focus from content to practice. Less focus on books and resources. The value is not in content but in the teaching around it. Open practices is more inclusive and active getting at core fundamentals around what it means to teach and learn such as knowledge sharing and critical thinking.

What Makes It Unique

The alliance's unique selling point would be its ability to serve as a central focal point for a fragmented community. By connecting national initiatives, communities of practice (like ALT in the UK), and policymakers, it can:

- **Strengthen existing communities:** It would be complementary to other existing organisations, providing a larger external alliance to amplify their work and provide a clearer entry point into a country's open education landscape.
- **Facilitate collective funding efforts:** It can help form coalitions and consortia to collectively pursue EU or other funding opportunities, which are often difficult for individual institutions to secure.
- **Shift the narrative:** The alliance can reframe the conversation around open education from being a niche topic to one that is central to the future of teaching, the role of AI, and the fundamental purpose of education itself. It can provide a more practical and inclusive narrative that goes beyond just open content (e.g. books) to include open practices and pedagogy.

4. Is there something an international (European) open education alliance could do that would help you accomplish your open education mission and goals?

An international open education alliance could significantly help achieve mission and goals by addressing key challenges that are difficult for individual institutions or national groups to tackle alone. The alliance's main role would be to act as a catalyst and central hub for policy, practice, and community building, fostering a truly open and collaborative European ecosystem.

Policy and Advocacy

The alliance could serve as a powerful voice for open education at the European level. By conducting a Europe-wide survey, it could map the current open education landscape. Where are their areas of overlap? How does an alliance interact with existing efforts? What is missing? Where could some efforts be added to build on what is there? Where is the opportunity? This data-driven approach would provide the evidence needed to:

- **Increase the visibility of open education** among key decision-makers and policymakers.
- **Expand access to funding opportunities** by creating consortia that can apply for EU or other grants.
- **Unify a European approach** to open education, which currently lacks a common definition, understanding, and process. Build a broad European movement that is uniquely open with a common direction. This includes addressing complex legal issues around copyright and ownership of faculty-created materials, a major barrier to progress.
- **Advocate for key changes**, such as ensuring that materials paid for with taxpayer money are open by default.

Collaboration and Community Building

The alliance would be instrumental in fostering a culture of collaboration and breaking down the silos that exist between institutions and networks. It could:

- **Create a shared digital infrastructure:** where subject specialists, developers, and learning designers from multiple universities can create, produce, share and maintain curricula of digital resources. A digital open education system that enables real collaboration between and across universities is crucial. Shared digital infrastructure for AI, for ensuring quality, and enabling adaptation and translation into other languages are needed. Can produce more together than going alone.
- **Facilitate peer learning and knowledge exchange:** By connecting experts from different countries, the alliance could help them learn from each other's successful

practices, especially in a wide range of areas such as vocational education or the integration of AI into curricula.

- **Provide safe spaces:** The alliance could create safe, open, and transparent forums for candid discussions about difficult topics like the balance between being open and the fear of commercial exploitation of one's work. These safe spaces, built on trust and a shared mission, would provide the confidence needed for individuals and institutions to fully embrace open practices.

Quality and Innovation

The alliance could address fundamental challenges related to the quality and relevance of open educational resources (OER) by:

- **Establishing quality criteria:** By developing and promoting quality criteria for digital materials, the alliance could help institutions ensure that their resources are high-quality, up-to-date, and trusted. This would address the common fear among academics that their work is not "good enough" to be shared widely.
- **Driving innovation:** The alliance could serve as a hub for experimentation and incubation, exploring new forms of open materials (e.g. modular, easily modifiable content). Curriculum development models and strategies need to be examined not just the resource. An alliance could co-create and share a curriculum for AI and pioneer new approaches to teaching and learning AI. Such activities would help move the field from a reactive to a proactive state, ensuring that open education remains at the forefront of educational innovation. Transformation is a big part.

In summary, an international open education alliance could act as a central node to unite and empower existing efforts, providing the collective strength needed to influence policy, drive large-scale collaborations, and address systemic challenges that are simply beyond the reach of individual organisations. This unified approach has the potential to create a powerful, coordinated movement that is essential for building a truly open and equitable European educational ecosystem.

5. Who should the alliance serve? Who should be the primary audience? Should there be limits on who can be part of such an alliance?

An international open education alliance should serve a diverse range of stakeholders, from students and teachers to policymakers and funding organisations.

Its primary audience should be the leaders at institutional and national levels who can drive systemic change, while also engaging practitioners to ensure the alliance's work is relevant and effective.

Who the Alliance Should Serve

The ultimate beneficiaries of the alliance's work are learners and professors. The alliance must serve them by raising awareness about the value of open education, providing high-quality resources, and helping them develop the skills to create, use, teach, and learn using open education. Create a groundswell of student interest and support for open education.

The alliance should also serve a wider ecosystem of stakeholders, including:

- **Developers and learning designers** who are essential for building and maintaining collaborative digital ecosystems and agreeing on licensing models.
- **Legal experts** who can help develop standards and resolve complex issues around licensing and intellectual property.
- **National and regional governments** whose strategies and policies can either enable or hinder the adoption of open education.
- **Intermediary organisations** that work on the ground and face similar challenges, providing a way to scale up local successes.
- **Funding organisations** which can be influenced to prioritize open as a default in their funding policies.

Primary Audience

The primary audience for the alliance's advocacy should be decision-makers at the highest levels. A top-down and bottom-up approach is needed to scale open education.

- **Senior Leaders:** Leaders at institutions, such as Pro Vice-Chancellors and rectors, need to be convinced of open education's value, as they are the ones who set the institutional agenda. This could be done through conferences and alliances that bring rectors and other representatives of higher education institutions together.
- **Policymakers:** National and commission-level policymakers are a prime audience. The alliance should build a bridge between these policymakers and practitioners to ensure that policies are informed by the realities on the ground.

- **Funding Organisations:** Influencing major funding bodies to adopt a default-to-open policy is crucial for making open education a priority.

Limits on Participation

The alliance should be an inclusive yet strategic group with clear safeguards against commercial interests.

- **Inclusion of Idealists:** The core of the alliance should consist of open education believers from public institutions and non-profit organisations who understand the culture shift of open education. People who are idealists motivated by the shared vision of open education rather than a profit-driven model.
- **Partnerships with Safeguards:** While partnering with vendors and solution providers is necessary, this must be done with safeguards. The alliance should set the direction of the collaboration, not be dictated by a commercial agenda.
- **Strategic vs. Community Partners:** The alliance should distinguish between strategic partners who can influence policy and a wider community that provides ground-level expertise. A small core group of national experts could co-create frameworks, with a broader audience of practitioners serving as a sounding board to ensure the work is relevant and effective.

6. What should the alliance not aim to do?

An international open education alliance should avoid certain pitfalls to ensure its effectiveness. It should not duplicate existing work or act as a vendor. Instead, it should act as an enabler, international convenor and influencer.

Key things to avoid:

- **Duplicating Existing Efforts:** The alliance must not replicate what other organisations or networks in Europe are already doing. Its mandate should be clearly defined to fill a unique niche and add value by bringing existing groups together.
- **Building a Product or Solution:** The alliance should not focus on building a product or open education solution. Instead, it should focus on building relationships and partnerships. A flexible, just enough, just in time technology is preferable to getting hung up and bogged down on a large, unwieldy ideal. Focus on interoperability and connecting things. Come at it from the practitioners perspective.
- **Commercial Exploitation of Openness:** The alliance should not include organisations that use open education as a tool to attract users only to later introduce fees or seek lock-in to their platform.
- **Getting Stuck in High-Level Goals:** While a clear mandate is essential, the alliance must avoid goals that are too high-level or vague, as this can prevent it from

achieving meaningful results. Its focus should be on practical, actionable items that address the needs of practitioners. Explicitly address the culture change associated with open education.

- **Unstructured Engagement:** The alliance should not engage with key stakeholders without a clear strategy. Collaboratively generate a memorandum of understanding including mission, vision, and mandate. Have alliance members provide feedback suggestions and sign off.

7. Would you be interested in participating in such an alliance? And if so, how?

International Stakeholders unanimously expressed interest in being part of an alliance though with a variety of caveats and conditions, including things like:

- aiming high
- if it creates a movement
- having an advisory role but the decision makers would come from rectors or higher education institutions themselves
- requiring buy-in from senior leadership
- creating mechanisms for expert working groups and topic chairs
- alliance serving as opener to countries that are not yet engaged with open. A “squad” could be created to make this happen.

8. Is there anything else you’d like to share with us about such an international open education alliance?

An international open education alliance should be more than just a collaboration; it needs to be a sustainable, values-driven organisation that provides tangible benefits to its members and the broader community. The following points summarise additional insights on building such an alliance.

Funding and Sustainability

- **Stable Funding is Key:** An alliance should not rely solely on voluntary, unpaid work. While in-kind contributions (sharing staff hours from existing organisations) can be a good starting point, the ideal solution is a stable, dedicated funding stream that supports an office and staff. This dedicated effort is crucial for maintaining momentum, as progress will be slow without it.
- **Shared Resources:** A hybrid model could work well: a central team funded by a stable source, supplemented by shared staff resources from member organisations. This model ensures core work gets done while leveraging the expertise of the wider network.

- **Feasibility and Simplicity:** It's important to keep the alliance's operational model simple and efficient. A complex governance or funding structure could become a barrier to progress.

Value Proposition and Engagement

- **Provide a Clear Value Proposition:** The alliance must offer a clear benefit to its members, especially practitioners. In an environment with job losses and reduced support, people need to know that their involvement is worthwhile. The alliance should help practitioners do their jobs better by providing resources, a network, and a sense of shared purpose.
- **Easy "Ins and Outs":** Given the demands on practitioners' time, the alliance should make it easy for people to get involved and disengage as needed. A flexible model encourages participation without overwhelming individuals.
- **Beyond Europe:** While a European focus makes sense due to existing initiatives and shared values, a truly global approach could provide even greater value by including diverse perspectives and addressing a wider range of challenges.
- **Building a Movement:** The alliance should aim to build a movement rooted in shared values, not just a collection of projects. This includes tackling issues of ownership, a common language, and the equitable distribution of knowledge in the age of AI. The ultimate goal is to create a vibrant, connected community that feels empowered to shape the future of open education.

ANNEXE D Communities of practice analysis

SPARC Europe analysed the following Communities of Practice:

1. Community College Consortium for Open Education Resources (CCCOER)
2. European Network of Open Education Librarians (ENOEL)
3. Open Education Network
4. Council of National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC)
5. UNESCO Open Educational Resources Coalition
6. Research Data Alliance (RDA)

A synopsis of the analysis of each community of practice follows.

Community of Practice #1: Community College Consortium for Open Educational Resources (CCCOER)

Website: <https://www.cccoer.org>

Strategic: CCCOER is a North American regional node of [Open Education Global \(OEGlobal\)](#), a membership-based organisation dedicated to promoting open education worldwide. OEGlobal has several regional nodes, including a Latin America LATAM regional node.

CCCOER [Strategic Plan 2025-2030](#)

The Strategic Plan guides CCCOER's activities, including:

- advocacy for open education
- community development
- professional training for open education scholars, practitioners, and students
- Implementation support for open education
- creation of online resources to support these and other open education efforts

CCCOER's vision is to ensure equitable access to high-quality education for all learners through openly licensed resources and open pedagogies that empower their success.

CCCOER's mission is to cultivate and engage a diverse network of educators, practitioners, and leaders who champion open education, fostering equitable and inclusive teaching and learning experiences.

Operational: OEGlobal provides the financial, legal, and infrastructure support to sustain CCCOER's efforts to promote the adoption of open education at community and technical colleges in North America.

Two OEGlobal staff members, a CCCOER Director and a Manager of CCCOER Communities provide operational support.

Annually, eight (8) volunteers serve on the CCCOER Executive Council. Additional volunteers serve on the CCCOER Standing Committees, and members are occasionally invited to participate in CCCOER working groups.

CCCOER currently has three Standing Committees:

- Equity, Diversity & Inclusion Committee,
- Professional Development Committee, and
- Research & Impact Committee

CCCOER has 88 member institutions across 31 states and provinces. If you are a member of CCCOER, you are also a member of CCCOER's parent organisation, OEGlobal.

Infrastructure to support CCCOER includes:

- [Website](#)
- [Community email listserv](#) is an opportunity to post questions about OER to the many expert practitioners in CCCOER and answer questions in your area of expertise. CCCOER also uses this group to share many online and some face-to-face meetups focused on open education, including free monthly webinars and advisory meetings. GoogleGroups hosts the email group. You can search the archives for past discussion topics. An [index of OER shared](#) via the email group has been created using the archives.
- [Discussion forum](#) (powered by Discourse)
- [YouTube channel](#) (recordings of webinars)

Activities: CCCOER runs from August through July to best match the academic year for many of its member institutions and consortia. Summer is a time for major and minor updates to the CCCOER website, committee planning, and more. In recent years, it has been a time for the EDI book club and informal conversations on topics of interest to our members. In August, CCCOER announces a schedule of fall webinars, new or renewed initiatives, and dates for upcoming quarterly CCCOER Member Newsletters.

CCCOER has produced a range of [OER tutorials](#) to support practitioner professional development.

In addition to webinars throughout the academic year on emerging open education topics, including specific topics suggested by members, there are quarterly member communications throughout the year. The member communications may feature a guest speaker/author, updates on national and global areas of interest, and an opportunity for members to share their plans or needs for growing their open education programmes.

OEGlobal has three major events each year in which CCCOER staff are actively involved, and all community members, including CCCOER members, are invited to participate. These events are:

- [Open Education Awards](#)
- [Open Education Week](#)
- [Open Education Global Conference](#)

Members of CCCOER lead a number of projects under the umbrella of OEGlobal. Projects include:

- [Open For Anti-Racism](#) grant funded by the Hewlett Foundation
- [Regional Leaders of Open Education Network](#) funded by the ECMC Foundation
- [California Consortium for Equitable Change in Hispanic Serving Institutions OER” \(CC ECHO\)](#), a project funded through the U.S. Department of Education’s Open Textbook Pilot programme.
- [California Zero Textbook Cost project](#)
- [Achieving the Dream OER Degree Initiative](#)
- [Case Studies](#)

Sustainability: CCCOER was founded in 2007. Eighteen years is a good long run as a community of practice, showing strength in purpose and maturity.

Membership fees contribute to the sustainability of CCCOER. Current annual membership fees are:

- Individual community/technical college or community college district (\$700)
- Regional Consortia (\$900 for consortia organisation, \$400 for each member institution that also joins)

OEGlobal provides the financial, legal, and infrastructure support to sustain CCCOER’s efforts to promote the adoption of open education at community and technical colleges in North America. OEGlobal is funded in large part by a general operating grant from the Hewlett Foundation.

Community of Practice #2: European Network of Open Education Librarians (ENOEL)

Website: <https://sparceurope.org/what-we-do/open-education/enoel/>

Almost 10 years old.

Strategic: ENOEL implements [SPARC Europe's OE STRATEGY 2024-2026](#) in its activities. The network's main goal is to bring academic librarians together as strategic partners in implementing the UNESCO OER Recommendation through collaborative knowledge sharing across borders in all of Europe. Librarians learn about OE and its benefit by collaborating with peers, co-creating resources, and co-facilitating events. Scope: countries within the UN-European Region

Operational: SPARC Europe provides financial support through Hewlett Foundation funding, limited legal support, and infrastructure support to sustain ENOEL's efforts to promote the adoption of open education at academic libraries in HEIs and universities of Applied Sciences in Europe.

One SPARC Europe staff member provides operational support for three days/week and another for half a day/week.

Activities:

- ENOEL members meet monthly to discuss activities, challenges, and opportunities
- Every resource ENOEL members create is shared with CC BY licence to promote reuse and adaptation.
- They co-design and co-create materials to advocate for OE and support upskilling (see below for more details and for links)
- They invite guests to discuss and promote open knowledge sharing around critical issues with champions in the field.
- They are co-creating an open textbook that reuses and repurposes educational resources, examining them through the lens of Universal Design for Learning to discuss how to improve them.

ENOEL outputs can be found as part of the [SPARC Europe Collection](#) (CC BY) on Zenodo, including:

- SPARC Europe's [Open Education Strategy 2024-2026](#)
- The [ENOEL Toolkit](#): a resource that supports Open Education advocacy by listing the evidence-based benefits that diverse stakeholders experience from Open Education. The Toolkit consists of slides, leaflets and cards that can be reused and adapted. It also offers playing cards with related gameplay to interact and discuss the Benefits more actively. The Toolkit exists in six versions and 22 languages.

- Survey instruments, data and reports on SPARC Europe's yearly efforts to map the developments in Open Education across Europe in [2021](#), [2022](#), and [2023](#).
- The report [*Insights into developments in European Open Education institutional policymaking \(2023\)*](#)
- “Embrace the Open” workshop series materials is run by and for ENOEL members and any participant interested in the topics wherever they are located. The educational materials created for these workshops and the workshop plan for each one are on Zenodo.

Recordings of events are available on [@ENOELforOpen YouTube Channel](#):

- ["Embrace the Open" workshops](#)
- [OE Champions](#) are interviews where European experts in Open Education share their experience and expertise with the audience
- [Open Mic podcast](#) episodes to disseminate the UNESCO OER Recommendation
- [OE Cafè](#) series with OE Champions at the European level, sharing their experience and discussing how to advance the implementation of the UNESCO OER Recommendation's action areas. We then continued inviting international guests and discussing important OE topics underlying the importance of having an active involvement of librarians
- [Under the Spotlight](#) series, with ENOEL members sharing their path in open education and inviting others to discuss starting from their experience.

Sustainability: The work of SPARC Europe’s staff members is covered through Hewlett funding. The work done by the majority of librarians is voluntary. A few can make time for ENOEL activities as part of their working duties in some institutions, but this is far from the default. More official involvement of libraries and their commitment to implementing the UNESCO OER Recommendation could make the work more sustainable and support building on the results achieved so far.

Community of Practice #3: Open Education Network

Website: <https://open.umn.edu/oen>

Strategic: The Open Education Network (OEN) is an open education membership organisation that advances the use of open educational resources and practices. Based at the University of Minnesota, the OEN works together with its members to make higher education more open. Members benefit from and contribute to the global open education ecosystem.

The network emerged from an initiative called the Open Textbook Library. The Open Textbook Library was started so faculty could find open textbooks in one place. A parallel support community called the Open Textbook Network was created with the launch of the Open Textbook Library in 2012. In 2020, the Open Textbook Network became the Open Education Network, acknowledging the growing importance of thinking about educational resources and the pedagogy that goes with them. While the OEN is focused on North America, it now supports the creation of OEN's in the UK and Australia.

Open Education Network (OEN) members commit to working together to make open the default in higher education. They seek to advance open education locally and collectively, empower faculty, remove barriers to education, and enhance student success. The OEN offers faculty engagement strategies, professional development, and infrastructure to make student learning more equitable and inclusive at an institution.

The OEN conducts a regular Community Scan, identifying challenges faced by the community along with community-identified suggestions for dealing with the challenges. The OEN compiles member responses and identifies next steps to be taken going forward.

Operational: The OEN has a set of guiding principles that guide and inform their actions, including:

- The Common Good
- Equity
- Inclusivity
- Action
- Humanity
- Integrity and,
- Shared Abundance

The Open Education Network has a team of staff, including an Executive Director, Director of Educational Programs, Digital Content Strategist, Senior Director of Publishing,

Developer, Director of Community Engagement, Program Coordinator, and Open Education Practices specialist.

The direction and activities of the OEN are guided by its members. Community leaders participate in a variety of ways, including:

- Committees: Steering Committee, Event Planning Committee, Pub101 Committee
- Workshops: facilitated by faculty and staff from member institutions with experience in implementing open education initiatives and practices.
- Advisory Groups
- Instructors: for Certificate programmes

The Open Education Network has 350 institutions, consortia, and regional system members, representing 1,886 campuses.

Infrastructure to support OEN includes:

- Website
- Open Textbook Library
- Open Pedagogy Portal
- Data Dashboard
- Open textbook publishing platforms
- Community of practice

Activities:

A core part of the Open Education Network is its Open Textbook Library. This library collection of open textbooks now houses over 1670 books across a wide range of higher education subject areas. All open textbooks are licensed by authors and publishers to be freely used and adapted. The Open Textbook Library makes these books available to download, edit and distribute at no cost.

When institutions join the Open Education Network, faculty are invited to review an open textbook. Faculty working at institutions and consortia who are members of the Open Education Network (OEN) submit reviews to the Open Textbook Library. Around 70% of books in the Open Textbook Library have been reviewed. In addition, library members of the OEN receive publishing support for authoring new open textbooks. Authors of open textbooks can submit their books for inclusion in the library.

The OEN has broadened beyond open textbooks to support the adoption of OER and open pedagogies.

The OEN provides a range of Supports and Resources, including:

- Professional development: Certificate in Open Pedagogy, Certificate in Open Education Librarianship, Pub101 Open Textbook Publishing, Learning Circles, Workshops
- Infrastructure: Open textbook library, data dashboard, publishing platforms (Ketty, Manifold, Pressbooks, Scribe)
- Community of Practice
- Colleague Connector Forum
- Community Hub events calendar and forum for virtual events

Sustainability: The Open Education Network was founded in 2020. It was formerly known as the Open Textbook Network, which started in 2012. The Open Textbook Library serves as the foundation for the Open Education Network and was also launched in 2012.

Membership fees contribute to the sustainability of the Open Education Network.

The Network has two membership types:

1. Institutional

Individual institutions enjoy direct access to the community and tools and resources to build and sustain open education programmes on your campus. If your institution is part of a library consortium, department of higher education, board of regents, or regional system that is an OEN member, institutional membership is available at a significantly reduced rate. \$1,914/yr (\$638/yr Reduced Rate*)

2. Consortial

As a library consortium, department of higher education, board of regents, or regional system, you'll enjoy similar benefits to institutional members and have the ability to select leaders to liaise with the OEN and share resources with your broader member community. \$4,467/yr

Community of Practice #4

Name: Council of National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC): <https://www.conosc.org>

Strategic:

CoNOSC brings together national OS leaders to engage in an international dialogue and share good practices for a stronger, more unified, and workable Open Science policy framework.

No public formal strategy, but one was developed based on interviewing national OS policymakers on needs in 2023.

The objectives and organisational principles of this network are:

- CoNOSC helps to fill in the gaps in national open science coordination through information, connection and collaboration.
- CoNOSC provides valuable insights on OS policy matters through dialogue with its members and other open science partners.
- CoNOSC membership is open to at least all countries within the UN-European Region.

The strategy was developed by interviewing national OS policymakers on needs in 2023.

Operational:

Facilitated by SPARC Europe since 2022.

There are over 30 members, including observers: EC, Science Europe (SE), and the European University Association (EUA).

The Memorandum of Understanding can be found here: <https://conosc.org/memorandum-of-understanding-mou/>

[The CoNOSC Board](#) has also included SPARC Europe since last year.

Activities:

SPARC Europe carries out / convenes the following:

- 3 meetings per year (one f2f) with 4-5 deep-dives on key policy areas
- [National policy overviews](#): Website
- Presentations on the status of OS policymaking, e.g for LERU
- Co-organised a closed webinar on OS and research security with Science Europe and EUA

- TF on Research Security
- Research: member needs, perhaps OS policy status in Europe
- Runs an internal members mailing list to facilitate info exchange

CoNOSC (SPARC Europe) is also an observer of the European University Association (EUA) EGOS working group. Attending meetings twice a year.

Sustainability:

SPARC Europe facilitation supported by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Space, France.

Members' in-kind contributions include policy updates, knowledge sharing, and hosting F2F meetings (Ireland 2023, Romania 2024, Slovenia 2025, Belgium 2026).

Community of Practice #5: UNESCO OER Dynamic Coalition

Website: <https://open.umn.edu/oen>

Strategic: The Open Educational Resources (OER) Dynamic Coalition was established in March 2020 by UNESCO's Communication and Information Sector to support the implementation of the first four areas of action defined in the 2019 UNESCO Recommendation on OER.

The OER Dynamic Coalition brings together stakeholders from Member States, including Ministries responsible for Education and/or Communication and Information Technologies, National Commissions to UNESCO, educational institutions and bodies, cultural institutions (including libraries, archives, and museums), Intergovernmental Organisations (IGOs), UNESCO Category 2 Centres, specialised institutions, civil society, and the private sector.

In March 2023, the UNESCO OER Dynamic Coalition was recognised as an official Dynamic Coalition of the [Internet Governance Forum \(IGF\)](#) - a global multistakeholder platform established by the UN Secretary General to facilitate the discussion of public policy issues about the Internet. As proud members of the IGF, we are committed to promoting OER adoption and usage, while building the capacity to access and utilise OER in line with the Global Digital Compact.

The main objectives of the UNESCO OER Dynamic Coalition are to:

1. Support the exchange of knowledge on ongoing activities - to raise the level of understanding on ongoing OER projects, networks, resources, and activities; and

2. Facilitate moderated collaboration on OER activities related to the five areas of Action of the OER Recommendation.

Operational:

- Members only
- No info about how it works on the website page on the UNESCO website
- They just launched a new portal in June, and anyone can register <https://oerdynamiccoalition.org/signup/unescooerdynamiccoalitionportal> (not mentioned nor linked in the main page on the UNESCO website). The portal aims to support knowledge exchange and collaboration on the activities of the OER Dynamic Coalition in the framework of the 2019 UNESCO Recommendation on OER. The principles of openness, accessibility, and multilingualism, as reflected in the UNESCO Recommendation on OER, are key to the exchanges on the portal.
- Stakeholders can ask to join by completing the [OER Dynamic Coalition Membership Form](#).
- Sending an email to Oerrecommendation@unesco.org, anyone can receive updates.

Activities:

- The OER Dynamic Coalition has launched a series of webinars to share knowledge and best practices in the OER Recommendation's different action areas.
- Dubai congress to discuss the impact of AI on OER and work on it (Dubai Declaration as a result)
- To enhance the visibility of the Recommendation's implementation activities, the Dynamic Coalition regularly publishes an Update to share information on OER events, projects, and initiatives of UNESCO and its partners at the global level.
- Big call to action in 2020 due to the pandemic, then quieter
- The recently launched portal is a sort of duplicate of the resources available on the main UNESCO website and channels, but it seems the intention is to make it grow.

Sustainability:

According to [UNESCO's Core Data Portal](#), the **OER Dynamic Coalition** is funded under a project with a **total budget of USD 600,000**, of which around **USD 536,394 has been expended** as of the latest update. The project launched on **15 July 2020** and is scheduled to run until **30 April 2025**. Funding comes from the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation.

Community of Practice #6: Research Data Alliance (RDA)

Website: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

Strategic:

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched in 2013 as a community-driven initiative with the vision that researchers and innovators can openly share and reuse data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address society's grand challenges.

Its mission is to build the social and technical bridges by creating, adopting and using the social, organisational, and technical infrastructure needed to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange.

Scientists and researchers collaborate with technical experts in focused Working Groups, exploratory Interest Groups, and Communities of Practice. Individual membership is free and open to all.

Has over 15,000 individual members from over 140 countries.

Almost 100 org members.

It has a **strategy for 2024-2028**:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/strategy/strategic-plan-2024-2028/>

Four themes: Globalise, Sustain, Empower and Innovate

And has [adoption stories](#).

Operational

Developed **governance structure**:

Its **Council** is responsible for the RDA's overall oversight, success, strategy, and sustainability.

A Technical Advisory Board acts as the RDA's technical backbone, offering expertise and guidance to the Council.

The **Organisational Advisory Board (OAB)** consists of representatives from the RDA's Organisational Members [and Affiliates](#). It represents their interests and ensures that their input and needs guide the RDA's programmes and activities.

The Regional Advisory Board (RAB) oversees the activities of both RAB and the Regional Assembly (RA). RAB advises the Council on issues of interest to the Regions and informs and steers the Council on regional issues.

The Secretariat is responsible for the administration and daily operations of the RDA.

Also has a [code of conduct](#).

Organised around regions: <https://zenodo.org/records/4297199>

From Interested to Engaged to Committed to Partners.

Activities:

- Over 60 working groups
- Over 70 Interest Groups (task forces: surveys, reports, case studies, statements, etc.)
- 2 CoPs (discipline-specific)
- Annual plenary meetings (f2f) - Brisbane, Oct 2025, London 2026

It has a [Recommendations and Output catalogue](#).

Sustainability:

Organisational membership fees

Grant funding

The Regional Engagement Strategy, launched in late 2018, aims to allow funders to support RDA on a regional and global basis (e.g. in the AU, EU, and USA).

Analysis: None of these communities acts as a European open education alliance. There are opportunities to learn from and work in partnership with some of these communities on open education advocacy and implementation.

A Community of Practice is a key means of collaborating in an Open Education International Alliance. Based on a SWOT analysis of all these communities of practice, the following recommendations regarding strategy, operations, activities, and sustainability are made.

Strategy	Operations
Purpose. Establish COP purpose. Collectively as a community, generate a vision, mission and strategy/priority-setting" that includes a work plan.	Dedicate staff (e.g. Director, Community Manager, Director of Community Engagement, Programme Coordinator, Administrator or other) to the Community of Practice (to liaise, organise, host, manage, facilitate, devise and implement a programme of events and activities).
Focus. Define the geographical and	Create community governance structures

<p>organisational breadth of membership. Focus on specific education sectors. Define organisational types eligible for membership. Identify members as multipliers in the first instance and large, prestigious networks. Take a staged approach to growing the network. Target specific stakeholders, understanding their needs.</p>	<p>(e.g. executive council, committees, working groups) that ensure the direction and activities of the COP are guided and led by community members themselves. Build member capacity in this area. Must be agile and not too bureaucratic, so defining terms would be essential.</p> <p><i>(Risks: members changing job roles vs. staff doing all the work. Member professional development and stepping into leadership roles.)</i> Consider recognition of CoP membership, e.g. badging.</p>
<p>Value Creation. Establish parameters for participation that ensure mutually beneficial value creation, collaborative effort, and open sharing. Clearly define the benefits of (regularly) participating and define ways of participating.</p>	<p>Identify, install and maintain digital infrastructure for the COP. Focus on IT that fosters relationship building between members of the COP (e.g. discussion, documentation and doc sharing, virtual presentation, resource sharing, collaboration, including multi-lingual tools, post and answer questions) and shared infrastructure related to alliance collaborative projects. Create a website that defines the community, what takes place there and how to become a member.</p>
<p>Consider establishing guiding principles or a code of conduct, including the public.</p>	
<p>Establish a membership acquisition plan - depends on size and focus.</p>	
<p>Consider how to monitor and measure COP impact (tangible and intangible).</p>	

Activities	Sustainability
Source activities from members and invite them to be presenters, facilitators, and knowledge exchangers. Encourage activity leadership amongst members over time.	Explore defining business model choices, such as annual membership fees that contribute to covering COP costs, and consider waiving or lowering fees in specific contextual situations.
Conduct workshops, webinars, and other forms of knowledge exchange. Consider developing and implementing a European OE capacity-building programme.	Identify ways for in-kind support where a member provides staffing, specific expertise, services, infrastructure, or some other support service and manage that.
Establish means for members to connect with each other (e.g. a listserv to support Q&A activity among members). This establishes relationships and allows members to quickly learn from each other.	Consider what is free to everyone, what is only available for members and what has additional costs (e.g. conferences, events).
Offer professional development (e.g. certificate programmes). Consider using existing open education certificate programmes available under an open licence for reuse (e.g. partnerships with existing certificate providers).	Explore partnerships with other communities for increased collaboration.
Define activities that allow for large or small commitments for a sound work balance. Enable episodic contribution and longer-term commitment by diversifying the level of engagement required.	Define an interim budget and work plan.
Host an annual event: for members/non-members.	
Consider targeting regional OE development and organising work within regions.	

Ideas we need to consider for the future:

- Help gain a better understanding of OE developments and challenges across Europe through research, such as desk research, survey/s, and interviews, for example, and also avoid activity overlap.
- Support aligned advocacy for broader OE adoption and consider building and implementing an OE advocacy programme.

ANNEXE E References made by interviewees on AI

“We need to advocate for open education being at the forefront of educational innovation, and connecting it to digital transformation and AI.” (pg 5)

“This includes tackling ownership issues, a common language, the integration of OER into curriculum design, and the equitable distribution of knowledge in the age of AI. This can form the basis of joint projects and funding efforts for European solutions to bigger problems.” (pg 6)

“An international alliance could be a very effective way of influencing AI and education legislation and policy at the European level.” (pg 16)

“This includes improving OER discoverability, tackling interoperability challenges, and effectively addressing the impact of emerging technological trends, such as AI, on open education. AI was especially mentioned many times as an obvious area of shared European interest.” (pg 32)

“Given its rapid evolution and global reach, AI development and its ethical, responsible use in education also necessitate international agreement on standards and practices.” (pg 46)

“The fundamental shift in teaching from traditional methods to open practices (and now AI) is a monumental cultural change.” (pg 46)

“Harmonising Policies and Practices: Duplication of efforts occurs when countries develop policies in isolation. International collaboration, potentially through a European committee, can lead to more unified policies, for example, regarding public values in sharing knowledge or AI agreements for learning materials.” (pg 48)

“Addressing Data and Content Ownership in the AI Era: With the rise of AI, the alliance must tackle critical issues like the ownership of data and content, particularly teacher copyright, and the transfer of ownership to publishers. There's a concern that AI will profit from open content without proper mechanisms. The alliance needs to explore new models to ensure students control their own data and to protect content from being "sucked into" commercial ecosystems.” (pg 57)

“The alliance can act as an intermediary consortium to set the direction of education in the age of AI.” (pg 59)

“This is essential for scaling up pockets of success and enabling the easy discovery, adaptation, and translation of OER. The alliance can also take the lead in addressing the responsible use of AI in this context, leveraging it to overcome technical barriers while working within clear guardrails.” (pg 60)

“The alliance can reframe the conversation around open education from being a niche topic to one that is central to the future of teaching, the role of AI, and the fundamental purpose of education itself.” (pg 62)

“A digital open education system that enables real collaboration between and across universities is crucial. Shared digital infrastructure for AI, for ensuring quality, and enabling adaptation and translation into other languages are needed.” (pg 63)

ANNEXE F Acknowledgements

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